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**CONVERSING WITH NON-HUMAN: A NARRATIVE INQUIRY ON THE USE OF
META AI AND CANVA AMONG PUBLIC SCHOOL TEACHERS**

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18 August 2025

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Acceptance Page

This paper prepared by **Lou Marie Karen Macabasco** with the title: **“CONVERSING WITH NON-HUMAN: A NARRATIVE INQUIRY ON THE USE OF META AI AND CANVA AMONG PUBLIC SCHOOL TEACHERS”** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree, Master of Development Communication.

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Biographical Sketch

Lou Marie Karen Macabasco is a graduate of Mass Communication (2018) from MSEUF Lucena. Her roles during her college years included serving as a student leader and an active member of the Mass Communication Society, where she held the position of officer, and as Secretary of the Department of College of Arts and Sciences for one term. She secured her television internship with ABS-CBN's Bayan Productions, Inc., specifically with Swak na Swak (Kabuhayang Swak na Swak). Choosing Mass Communication is a bold choice, as she believes in the power of stories and creating a platform that unites people. During college, apart from academics, her participation in organizations provided great opportunities for meaningful engagement with students, empowering them to discover their potential.

She obtained her Civil Service (Professional) eligibility a year after graduating (2019).

Previously, she held the role of Corporate Strategy Associate at a creative agency (MSocial, Inc.), working with cross-functional teams as she assisted with business client relations in the Events Department of the agency.

Driven by purpose, she began her Master's Program, exploring communication from various perspectives and challenging herself academically to grow both professionally and personally. By doing so, she gained expertise that contributes to the field of communication, opening more opportunities for leadership roles.

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First and foremost, I want to thank God for the endless wisdom, guidance, and assurance that led me to bravery. Everything asked of him, he listens, with confidence and independence. I continue to trust everything will fall into place.

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UPOU, the dream I had in my head has become a reality as I entered here. Thank you for sharing this dream with me; now, allow me to take my dreams outside and meet more people with the same values and drive for change.

Dedication

For my parents' unwavering support and patience as I embark on finishing my Master's. To my sisters who supported me throughout. To my friends who showered me with affirmations and words of encouragement. For now, I can proudly say, "Nanay and Tatay, may U.P. Graduate na kayo!"

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ABSTRACT

Anchored in narrative inquiry as a meaning-making process, this study restoryed and examined the narratives of 10 elementary school teachers in Laguna, exploring how they communicate with digital tools like Meta AI and Canva and how these tools shape their instructional practices. Although AI's role in the education landscape is increasing, only a few studies have explored teachers' engagement with these applications and the motivation behind it. The effects that take place after interacting with these applications contribute to the personal changes in the teachers' new reality, prompting the need for this study. Teachers' utilization of the application was based on the perceived role and identity AI has in their lives, from being a mentor, doctor, personal assistant, etc., executing human-capable roles; nevertheless, using the information generated by AI is at the teachers' discretion and trust of AI's capability, understanding AI has its limitations. Findings revealed that teachers primarily use AI for lesson planning, generating visual aids, and simplifying content preparation. They described prompting AI as an interactive, trial-and-error communication process that requires critical judgment. Teachers noted that AI helped them shift from traditional to digital methods, but also expressed skepticism about the accuracy and appropriateness of AI-generated outputs. The study also showed that AI reshapes teachers' professional identity by expanding their role as content curators and decision-makers, rather than solely as authors. Human autonomy strengthens the regulation of AI application usage. These experiences shape the design of teaching materials and teachers' openness to integrating emerging technologies into instruction.

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

Rationale and Background of the Study

Sampson et al. (2022) define communication as the exchange of symbols and meaning. Ideally, the communication process involves a sender (the source), a receiver (the person toward whom the message is intended to be received), a channel, and an effect.

However, communication in the 21st century has evolved beyond traditional interaction methods. What if they talk to a non-human entity, such as artificial intelligence (AI)? Does it follow the same communication process when speaking with machines? Or, on the contrary, *are humans progressively adapting to AI's language?*

Artificial Intelligence is a technology that has learned to interpret vast amounts of data, which allows it to think and learn. It refers to human intelligence; hence, the way they reason and perform tasks is deeply rooted in the information they are fed (Hofmeyer, 2024).

AI is an interdisciplinary branch of computer science that can carry out complex tasks and has been effectively applied across various industries, from advertising to healthcare, due to its assistive applications (Moore, 2019). The teaching profession, undoubtedly, would have also taken advantage of using AI.

Due to advanced technology, *AI is increasingly having more communicative roles*, and once associated with human interactions, the larger scale affects society,

and the more of this continues to happen, the more theories and concepts are needed to explain the phenomenon (Guzman & Lewis, 2020)

AI is more involved in people's lives than they think, from waking up in the morning and opening their mobile devices to checking search engines for the latest news or updates. Even the shows watched involve AI usage (Marr, 2021). It has been a convenience in doing one's daily tasks. Living in a fast-paced environment, people have integrated technology into their daily lives, making it a key player in the transformative technological evolution (Lawson, 2023).

AI communication has been a focus due to its immense potential and its integration into one's everyday routine. People rely on AI applications to perform small tasks or assist them daily, much like a personal assistant, to the extent that they become their go-to friend or the new Google for searching for anything or asking a trivial question. Hence, learning to effectively communicate with these AI applications (Meta AI and Canva) would benefit society.

Suffice it to say that teachers are no exception. AI tools are personal assistants that can enhance the lives of teachers, who are expected to develop engaging and relevant instructional materials on a daily basis. Anchored in Human-Computer Interaction, a multidisciplinary field focused on the design and evaluation of computer systems, this study identified the factors influencing why teachers use AI applications and what transpires from these conversations/interactions (Simplilearn, 2023).

Learning how people communicate with AI and to what extent it is being used should be studied to determine the direct effects on how teaching has been

shaped/changed (Marr, 2021). Two AI tools that teachers popularly use are Meta AI and Canva. Meta AI operates by utilizing users' prompts to generate responses based on the questions and information it has stored in its datasets. However, Meta AI would respond engagingly, like talking with a human. Meta AI chatbot is built into social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp. It has been free to dozens of countries (Caswell, 2024).

Canva, on the other hand, is a free online graphic design tool that offers features such as AI image generation, text prompts, and image editing tools. Magic Media enables the creation of a creative vision that is immediately generated (Adams, 2023). Thus, generative AI has helped produce new content and materials. Businesses have found that generative AI helps create marketing materials and templates, which they then utilize in digital social media posts (Toloka Team, 2023). Teachers can use this application to develop class instructional materials without having to start from scratch. Teachers can even use the platform for free as long as they are handling K-12 levels. Approved and signed by Education Secretary Sonny Angara, the partnership with Canva Philippines for Canva for Education has been operational, providing public school teachers with free access to and training on the application (Department of Education, 2024).

AI has much to offer, as it proposes new ideas, learns new things, and brings visions into reality. To further understand human and machine communication from the teachers' point of view, this study aimed to investigate why teachers utilize AI, what occurs during their conversations, whether AI usage influences their actions, and how they perceive AI applications. Teachers go out of their way to support their students to get the best education and training possible. This is being done to ensure

that they are equipped as they move from one grade level to another. Teachers use AI applications for various personal reasons, one of which is to enhance their teaching and support educational tasks. By learning why they chose to communicate and what they communicate about, a more profound understanding of the effects of human-machine interaction is gained, including the changes that occur, and a more precise grasp of the reality behind why AI applications should be understood.

Statement of the Problem

As technology progresses and technological advances like AI become more prominent in usage, AI is expected to be more potent in the coming years (Giattino et al., 2023). As a new application tool, teachers should be well-versed in determining the accuracy of AI responses rather than mindlessly following them, especially when pressed for time.

Developing new ideas, graphics, and engaging visuals requires diligence and extra time for teachers to improve their lessons. While these lessons are included in their books, the pictures are unclear, and the colors are too challenging to depict reality. Searching for more suitable materials may take some time, but with AI, the response is swift, and the generated responses can be efficiently utilized.

The Digital Era brings unprecedented technological developments and modern advancements. AI applications are now an integral part of daily life and are expected to become increasingly normalized. Recognizing this reality, developing the ability to effectively communicate and utilize platforms such as Meta AI and Canva constitutes a strategic investment that will benefit both current and future users.

Discovering how teachers communicate with AI applications like Meta AI and Canva contributes to learning the teaching and learning process. Thus, the study aimed to answer the question: “How do public school teachers communicate with digital tools like Meta AI and Canva, and how do these applications shape their instructional practices?”

Objectives of the Study

The study sought to:

1. Examine teachers’ intentions for using Meta AI and Canva in their instructional practices;
2. Describe the communication process involved when teachers prompt and interact with Meta AI and Canva;
3. Explain the role of AI in mediating human interaction within the context of teaching; and
4. Analyze the ontological contributions of AI to teachers’ professional behavior and identity.

Significance of the Study

While teachers know the information to be shared or taught, AI applications like Meta AI and Canva provide quicker responses to questions or reading that need synthesis, especially for students studying or pursuing their master's or doctoral degrees. The presence of these AI applications is here to stay. Knowing how teachers communicate with these applications can also inform us what can be learned from non-human communication.

From a development communication perspective, the continuous use of AI applications can help train AI to recognize what data should be included in their database, ensuring the accuracy of results. Understanding how teachers

communicate with AI helps these applications generate correct information for use in the teaching-learning process.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

The AI application tools were limited to Meta and Canva, which are the most popularly used. The study did not delve into teachers' computer literacy or technical competence. The study also did not examine what gadgets they use or where they access these tools. It was conducted in only one public school, the name of which was not divulged for anonymity to prevent speculations or stigma about why teachers use AI when they discourage students from using it. The study did not examine this double standard of teachers employing AI tools while denying students the same opportunity.

The study focused more on how communication takes place with non-humans or conversations between teachers and either Meta AI, Canva, or both.

Chapter 2

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Artificial Intelligence and Its Applications

AI is evolving, and technologies are creating application software for public use. It is divided into two categories: capabilities (Artificial Narrow AI, General AI, and Super AI) and functionalities (Reactive Machine AI, Limited Memory AI, Theory of Mind, and Self-aware AI) (IBM Data & Team, 2023).

Adaptability is a strength in a world that continues to progress in technology. Lembke (2024) explained that being digitally fit is needed to conquer the future. If the future of communication involves AI, then people in this generation should develop the ability to adapt and make conscious decisions to interact and communicate effectively with AI.

Meta announced the rollout of Meta AI, including the Philippines, on October 9, 2024. Currently, Meta AI is available. It is similar to OpenAI's GPT-4, but with Meta AI, other social media applications would have access to Meta AI for free. These apps are Facebook, Instagram, Messenger, and WhatsApp (Arasa, 2024). The Meta AI bot would function like a personal assistant, helping people with tasks such as recommending restaurants or assisting with studying for a test (Arasa, 2024).

Meta AI is designed to help give accurate answers to various questions. Due to its advanced natural language processing, Meta AI can deliver informative responses (Tridevi, 2024). Writing prompts to Meta AI can help generate content, such as email messages, social media posts, or articles. Furthermore, Meta AI could

assist with language translation, content summarization, conversation, or look-up for suggestions from another perspective. Additionally, even if one is not skilled in the arts but has an expansive imagination, Meta AI can help create and generate it (Tridevi, 2024).

AI usage involves familiarizing oneself with how to communicate with AI apps to submit requests. Sometimes, requests should be more specific so that the task asked, for example, images related to art, can be addressed. If you are looking for something specific, such as a particular color or a specific author, AI can answer queries or provide the right suggestions (Visual Journalism Team, 2023).

AI applications, such as Meta AI, are similar to search engines; the primary difference is that search engines provide a wide range of suggestions related to the query, whereas AI applications directly answer the query. Search Engines will provide answers to questions and offer recommendations related to the topic being asked, with information that contains the keyword (Tarapara, 2023).

Canva can be accessed through a web browser or an app on a mobile device, allowing users to create presentations. Launched in 2013, Canva has continuously evolved, adapting to new technologies and innovations. This has included the integration of AI features, enabling users to generate art using prompts. Canva is ideal for content creation and presentations.

Even if one is not an artist by profession, such as a student or a teacher, Canva's user-friendly features make it accessible to everyone (Edwards, 2024).

Canva already offers virtual templates for you to choose from. Users can opt to use or upload their images and design them within the application. Usage is not limited to creating visual presentations, such as posters; users can also record video presentations directly within the application. The drag-and-drop options developed in

the application made it easier to visualize the assets and place them on the blank canvas. Speeches, report presentations, and typing ideas (prompt) should be easy. Canva is a good application (Edwards, 2024).

Canva's latest tool is Dream Lab, linked to its acquisition of Leonardo AI. Dream Lab creates visuals from simple text descriptions provided by the user. It can generate and offer fifteen different styles based on the user's description (Stokes, 2024).

Human-Computer Interaction

Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) is concerned with understanding how people interact with machines, focusing on the computer's design interface and its impact on users. Its primary goal is to produce reliable and secure computer systems. The success of HCI is determined by the level of satisfaction that users experience when interacting with the product. The relationship between AI and HCI falls in the spectrum between human-computer interaction and intelligent systems (Sadiku et al., 2021)

This study defined a computer as any computing technology (from desktops to large-scale computers). Interacting with computers in various ways, such as through keyboards, mice, tablets, or mobile devices, in most cases, the graphical user interface has been the primary focus, as it is more visual (Sadiku et al., 2021).

Practical AI applications require HCI skills to integrate AI techniques into their interface development. Recognition of both fields served their purpose (Abolkasim & Ramachandran, 2021).

A study by Mutmainnah et al. (2022) examined learning and teaching English as a foreign language (EFL). It has been observed that student-centered learning

promotes higher-order thinking, enabling students to learn and adapt more effectively to the language. Incorporating traditional teaching and digital communication methods has helped improve students' learning capabilities. The HCI is involved here as students and teachers utilize AI teaching materials efficiently, tailored to their specific needs.

Similarly, a study by Chenna (2023) discussed improving augmented reality (AR) and AI by enhancing human-computer interaction through the creation of more immersive virtual experiences powered by AI, as well as developing virtual characters and objects that interact naturally with users. Further development could transform different industries. Thus, it can be inferred that AI and HCI are closely intertwined in development, offering greater benefits to humans.

Theories like Activity Theory and Mental Models help relate to this context of communication between humans and machines.

Activity theory explains how AI applications are not passive; they interact with other components of a system. Achieving goals through the use of tools as actions occurs within a larger system. For example, the subject is the teacher; aside from knowing the tools used (AI applications), outside factors, such as coworkers, are considered part of the community, and task division (division of labor) factors are considered within the larger system. This theory explains how these elements work together and the changes that occur when using the tool, making work easier or faster, which in turn makes the goal (object) easier to attain (Kaptelinin, 2014).

Mental Models, on the other hand, are the ideas people have about how something works. For example, a user's understanding of what they think Meta AI and Canva are capable of deeply reflects in how the user uses the application, given

their prior knowledge or belief. Emotional and cognitive decisions influence how users interact with the application (Interaction Design Foundation, 2016).

AI functions the way humans expect it to function. Various factors affect the end-product depending on how the AI application is used and perceived.

Communicating with Non-Human

Communicating with a non-human requires a specific approach that needs to be clear and detailed, as machines cannot particularly understand one's sense of humor or identify with the tone of one's voice to discern what was meant. Typing a straightforward and direct-to-the-point question should do the trick. By this method, AI enhances the app experience as it progresses and processes large amounts of information about the query, aiming to personalize the experience for subsequent conversations or interactions (Capitol Technology University, 2024).

Like customer service chatbots that answer queries, AI bases its suggestions on previous interactions to give a more personalized conversation with the customer. AI bases its recommendations on the information the user shares, such as their gender, age, interests, and links they have interacted with. This provides AI with a suggestion based on the user's interest (Capitol Technology University, 2024).

In the podcast "Think Fast, Talk Smart," host Matt Abrahams released an episode in August 2024 regarding the future of communication. His guest for this segment was Russ, a bioengineering professor at Stanford. Russ shares his personal experience dealing with AI as they discuss the topics.

Altman builds on the discussion of the **future of communication, as AI** usage has been put in the spotlight due to issues arising concerning information and communication. He then touches on the issue of AI replacing humans like the

ChatGPT tool, as discussion happened, he throws back the idea to its listeners by saying that if it ever crosses anyone's mind that AI would replace humans, it is that humans need to evaluate their purpose, ask what their reasons are for doing things, and the things they communicate. One should not be afraid if one knows what they are trying to do. (Abrahams & Altman, 2024).

As the discussion continued, Abrahams confirmed that if Altman uses this type of AI app (like ChatGPT), he will proceed to share his experiences and on-air highlight a story about writing his grant. He mentioned how he sought guidance from his colleague, but then passed it through the LLM (Large Language Model) for checking. He uses it to summarize the strengths and weaknesses of the grant, helping to identify gaps he may have missed during the writing process (Abrahams & Altman, 2024).

After the interview, he calls attention to Altman's advice about focusing on the individual purpose using AI and communicating with that purpose.

Research from Hohenstein et al. (2023) titled "Artificial intelligence in communication impacts language and social relationships" shows a difference as this discusses a more profound connection of human interaction with machine that could affect interpersonal relationships, the result of the study shows how AI system can help with generating smart replies one that can reply to a person, but this lead unintentionally to social consequences and disconnection to the person receiving the response. AI has its way and ability to help communicate quickly, but alongside this are the emotional alterations in language and patterns that occur over time. This leads to a mindset that depends on how one views AI, its usage, and the extent to which it can be utilized.

The study by Jiang et al. (2024) explores human-AI collaboration. It highlighted the differences between humans and AI in terms of skills; this study emphasized how humans and AI collaborate to achieve a common goal. As humans contribute to the cognitive, creative, and ethical judgment aspects, AI excels in pattern recognition, data analysis, and making future predictions, which leads to a superior outcome compared to either human or AI working alone. *Human-AI collaboration enhances jobs by taking the burden off or offloading dangerous tasks, which allows humans to focus on more complex work (cognitively).* Collaboration is not a bad idea; it shows how humans and AI working together can yield satisfactory results, as each other's weaknesses become each other's strengths.

Continuance of development helps in perfecting applications. Chatbots have improved and evolved over the years, from simply handling numerous conversations and responding to prompts to conversing in a person's native language. The study by Adamopoulou and Moussiades (2020) tackles chatbots. The knowledge acquired by chatbots influences how they structure their sentences, and their ability to answer questions depends on the extent of their learning. If, due to a lack of sufficient data, it cannot be concluded that a clear answer can be given, it is because of this limitation.

AI-human communication varies, as chatbots can only answer the information they are programmed to provide. Professor Kenji Sagae examined the impact of large language models (LLMs) on society from a linguistic perspective. It is assumed that if the LLM is trained on data from the US web pages, knowledge adapted from culture, values, and biases would appear and reflect the US (Russell, 2024).

LLM is a subset of Machine Learning (ML). The application process differentiates the two. LLM is more inclined towards language understanding

(chatbots, text summarization), while ML is focused on structured data analysis (interpretable data) and analytics (Novita.Ai, 2024).

Sagae observed that the **interactions between AI and humans** can influence how humans communicate, a notable side effect. As interactions become more frequent with computers than with humans, this has an impact on children who are starting to learn and adapt to communicate through language. As children grow and learn a language outside the community, they may come to know it without emotions, attachment, and feelings connected to their environment (Russell, 2024).

The use of AI applications varies depending on who is using them, for what purpose, and the guidance provided for their use. A study conducted by Brandtzaeg et al. (2022) demonstrated how users of the AI application Replika redefined the concept of friendship in a human-AI context and compared it to human-to-human friendships.

Conversational artificial intelligence has contributed to understanding friendships, similarities, and differences in reciprocity, intimacy, and trust. Findings reveal that human-AI friendship prioritizes personalization and availability over reciprocity and shared experiences. Replika can tailor to users' needs as a chatbot, but it lacks and is limited in free will. Unlike human friendships, users perceive the relationship with Replika as beneficial for emotional support and self-disclosure. Another thing to note is that, since it is available anytime, forming a connection is instant (Brandtzaeg et al., 2022).

Human-AI interaction forms bonds beneficial to both. In the article by Liu (2024), the author discusses the outlook of using ChatGPT in human-computer interaction and from a psychological perspective. ChatGPT originated from OpenAI, and this AI is trained using the knowledge fed to it, as well as through human

interactions with the chatbot. From a psychological perspective, ChatGPT has been perceived by users as a support tool. As the application develops into a more sophisticated conversational capability, partly due to this, the user may become more dependent on it and resort to fewer interpersonal connections. With technology, it is essential to strike a balance of usage as it continues to progress.

There are still many uncertainties surrounding AI usage, and optimizing it to its full potential depends on continuous advancements in hardware, software, laws, and policies that shape AI's role in communication and utilization. Hence, it is essential to address the challenges it poses and understand its impact on users, including trust, deception, language use, and relationships, focusing on critical areas that will enable the design, implementation, and regulation of AI systems to the advantage of humans (Hancock et al., 2020).

Influence on Human Communication

AI is undoubtedly shaping and influencing human communication, with individuals increasingly adapting their communication to incorporate technology. Guzman (2020) highlighted that the ontological boundaries between humans and computers, as well as their implications for human-machine communication, are not static. The criteria that differentiate humans from computers in communication are subject to change, as AI continuously learns and evolves in its interactions with humans. Therefore, Guzman's study emphasized the implications of the divide that emerges during human-machine communication.

Furthermore, the study provided data collected from the respondents to categorize how humans and machines can be differentiated, from their origin to intelligence and down to emotions. Questioning who is smarter was never the topic,

as the respondents saw how humans and computers have intelligent qualities. Additionally, the findings highlighted the importance of the ontological boundary in human-machine communication. People's understanding of the difference contributes to how they view AI as a technology that communicates with humans, informing their decisions through the human-machine communication process.

Now, people have a choice in how they communicate with technology and what they expect from it (Guzman, 2020). As AI continues to progress rapidly, it is essential to consider how different AI systems will evolve in the future. The environment, personality, and social dynamics are crucial in shaping how individuals respond to AI-based persuasive intentions (Asif & Goqing, 2024). Understanding these factors is essential for predicting and influencing human reactions to AI-driven persuasion.

Researchers are focusing on understanding these changes and applying them to new technologies. They are learning that communication is more complex than sending and receiving messages. AI's role in persuasion and communication is influenced by a few factors, such as technology, information sources, human attitudes toward AI, and the environment (society and social media). AI fostering deeper relationships with humans alters the social dynamics of human-AI interactions, influencing how humans interact with AI and other people (Asif & Goqing, 2024).

Similarly, Danso et al. (2023) explained that technological innovation has had a direct impact on communication over the years, with advancements in technology also driving human development. The systematic literature review (SLR) checks the role of AI in human communication. Advancements in data have allowed AI to automate communication processes effectively.

Advances in technology have been a lever in its adoption. This SLR highlights that AI is transforming human communication as it gains the ability to learn and adapt, enabling it to converse more humanely. This review stressed the importance of reviewing and organizing ethical and responsible development for AI.

AI-mediated communication transforms humans' interactions, influencing language, tone, messaging, societal norms, and trust. For example, Gmail now suggests responses and offers options to tailor the tone of a message, such as positive, formal, or apologetic. While this innovation has many benefits, it also raises concerns. AI can reinforce biases and call into question the authenticity of communication. For instance, when users browse Airbnb listings, they may hesitate to engage with a host whose profile appears AI-generated, preferring a more personal connection rather than interacting with what feels like a computer (Erensoy, 2021).

There are many opinions about AI and its usage, but it all comes down to what happens in communication. Sarwari et al. (2024) studied the impact of AI on various aspects of life, with a particular focus on communication. The concern here is whether AI can be used for interaction (language translation), if, in the long run, it helps with these interactions, or if using AI complicates the communication process. This study assessed the impact of AI on intercultural communication among postgraduate students in a multicultural university environment.

One hundred fifteen postgraduate students from nine countries participated in the study. Using quantitative and qualitative surveys, the study revealed that 93% of participants used AI technologies, specifically ChatGPT, and 87.7% responded that AI had helped connect diverse cultures, reduce cultural barriers, and facilitate interaction between them (Sarwari et al., 2024).

These respondents utilized AI to overcome the cultural barrier among participants, enabling them to connect in a shared language, learn about each other's cultures, and effectively use this tool to complete their school tasks. It has been observed that how participants perceive AI and how AI is regulated affects the benefits they derive from using it. Results show a positive correlation between AI attitude, AI benefits, and AI regulation. Respondents want to address ethical concerns over AI usage, but more importantly, regulating AI usage enhances the effectiveness of intercultural communication (Sarwari et al., 2024).

The AI-human relationship is based on *human interaction and perception of AI*. How one interacts with AI, with a category of AI acting as more socially beneficial or intellectually superior, suggests that the way a human interacts with another human is a factor in how they interact with AI. Varying from different perspective biases and answers of AI to the person depends on their learned behavior and how this individual treats them.

Results show that AI fairness positively affects perceptions of warmth (or, in this study, socially good or bad traits) towards its principal (human). This effect was devised due to the human-AI interaction's group cohesion (activity).

Furthermore, this study also contributes to understanding how behavior influences social perception and interpersonal communication. While humans shape AI as we interact with it, it can design and shape human relationships in Artificial Intelligence-mediated communication (Li et al., 2023).

How others perceive AI depends on how they utilize it themselves.

The 2021 UKRI report highlights the impact of AI on research, raising concerns over research quality and efficiency, and demanding adjustments for researchers and their studies. Focusing on measurable outcomes may overshadow

human aspects such as curiosity, fairness, and emotional investment in research (Chubb et al., 2022).

AI inclusion in research must be defined if the focus is on *quality over quantity*. Human decisions play a critical role in AI's impact and learning within the research community, particularly when AI is perceived as being disadvantageous to use. AI's role as a support should not overpower the meaning and goal of why research is done, so that output demands can be met. The research value should not be compromised, as it will impact the study's objectives (Chubb et al., 2022).

AI usage should not overshadow the broader context of why such a task is being undertaken; it should be viewed as a tool to enhance the overall picture, which can evolve and change, but not restrict, what could be.

AI's communicative endeavor thrives on human interaction. It learns from data fed to it, but this sometimes leads to constraining a person's identity. The study by Valenzuela et al. (2024) demonstrates how AI can unconsciously limit people's options regarding what information to consume, thereby shaping their identity.

For example, when viewing one's favorite show, typing a specific genre prompts AI to recommend shows with similar genres. If the user (person) only takes what is given to them, moving forward, they will only get one type of genre without thinking of the other. Overdependence on AI can limit people's autonomy and cause them to lose their sense of identity (Valenzuela et al., 2024).

AI can help shape a person, and it can revolutionize industries such as business operations. The literature review by Perifanis and Kitsios (2023) examines the impact of artificial intelligence in the digital era, particularly in business, and how technology has facilitated these changes and improvements. Harnessing AI's potential requires understanding how it works, how to communicate, and being

willing to question established norms and explore uncharted territories. This was particularly evident during the COVID-19 pandemic, when established business strategies were abandoned due to the unviable circumstances. AI opened new avenues, bridging the gap between staying ahead of the curve and adapting to the ever-changing landscape of technology.

AI-human collaboration is crucial as technology advances in data processing and automation. Working together means humans focus on strategic and creative tasks. Despite the benefits, challenges such as privacy, bias, and labor market changes must be addressed appropriately as AI usage is regulated, leading to a sustainable and advanced society (Lu, 2023).

Theoretical Lens

This study is grounded in the multidisciplinary field of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) theory. Focused on how people use digital systems, how technology can be designed to meet their needs, and how this technology impacts human behavior and welfare (Damyanov, 2023).

One of the pioneers of HCI is Douglas Engelbart. He believed computers could enrich human intelligence, and studying human-computer interaction is a critical component. HCI will continue to develop interfaces and systems that enhance user interaction, making digital interactions intuitive and accessible (Damyanov, 2023).

In relation where Meta AI and Canva a popular digital tool used by teachers, HCI as lens of this study lead to the discovery of learning what has convinced the teachers to use these digital tools, how they communicate effectively, with interacting from these AI applications what has transpired, and what is the effect of this

discovery on the teachers perspective on how AI applications have shaped their actions and identity in constructing their new reality.

Ongoing research in HCI (Human-Computer Interaction) focused on improving the usability of computer systems and understanding how cognitive processes relate to both natural and artificial intelligence, creating stronger relationships for human-computer interaction (Alkathairi, 2022).

HCI promotes inclusivity, ensuring everyone (even people with disabilities) gets equal access to technology and services. This is beneficial because, as new technologies emerge, HCI encourages the development of user-friendly interaction methods, evolving with trends by enhancing the decision-making process, improving data visualization, and making complex data easier to interpret (Simplilearn, 2023).

This study examined how teachers navigate and experience using Meta AI and Canva — exploring their reasons for choosing these tools, the purpose behind their use, and the meanings that unfold through this interaction.

Philosophical Assumptions

This study aligns with the research paradigm, grounded in the philosophical element of ontology, which examines the nature of reality and human engagement in the world (Alele et al., 2023). Ontology deals with the nature of being. As ontology deals with the nature of human existence, particularly in relation to social interaction and communication, the core of ontology lies in how the communicator is perceived (Littlejohn & Foss, 2011).

The current reality is multifaceted; with the rise of AI, many possibilities have become available. Applications like Meta AI and Canva are a few examples that exist in the "Digital Era," where technology is shaped by technological advancements and

the users who utilize it. This interaction shapes the user's behavior in line with their actions and decision-making.

Chapter 3

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A narrative inquiry was employed in this qualitative study. The core of narrative inquiry lies in living, telling, and reliving the stories. Retelling stories through inquiry, reliving the experiences felt (Clandicini & Huber, 2023). Using a narrative approach, participants shared their stories and perspectives, utilizing these AI applications to perceive and make sense of their experiences and the value/lesson (Bhandari, 2024).

A narrative inquiry was used to analyze how teachers interact/communicate with Meta AI and Canva. The qualitative approach focused on the individual experiences of the teachers and their stories using these AI applications, through one-on-one interviews. With one-on-one interviews, every individual can share their perspective in a comfortable setting. Their observed behavior is a key component in analyzing the meaning behind their perspective and actions that result from their communication with AI applications.

A Qualitative approach is non-numerical and unstructured. The study's data came from the open-ended responses of the research respondents (Dye, 2021).

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted at a Public Elementary School in Laguna, where teachers were asked to participate in this research for data gathering. In safeguarding their identity, the name of the school will remain anonymous.

Selection of Participants

The participants were teachers from a school in Laguna who are knowledgeable about and have used Artificial Intelligence applications, such as Meta AI or Canva. Ten elementary school teachers in Laguna who met the following criteria were interviewed:

1. Teacher in Elementary;
2. Have experienced teaching using traditional methods; and
3. Have used Meta AI, Canva, or both for their teaching profession.

Data Gathering

The data collection method used was through personal interviews. Using a semi-structured approach, which allowed for follow-up questions when the interviewee raised points that piqued interest, provided a deeper understanding and knowledge of the research, and led to additional questions being raised and discussed (StudySmarter, 2024).

This study achieved promising results using a qualitative approach; in-depth interviews brought perspectives from the participants' experiences, reflections, reactions, and insights. A semi-structured interview provided a balance of steady workflow, as it guided participants' answers to open up new subtopics that helped inform this research (George, 2023).

Along with focusing on the narratives of each participant, their behaviors during the interview were also observed and considered as part of the data-gathering process. Humans communicate with words, but their actions also convey information; their non-verbal cues provide insight and bearing while they share their point of view.

Part of the interview involved asking participants to share their one interaction with Meta AI or Canva, providing a screenshot or photo as additional support for how their conversation went, and discussing the end products, such as visual aids created using the application. Transcription was done after data collection.

Data Analysis

Narrative inquiry focused on making sense of human experience through personal stories. Active interviews were used as it was acknowledged that the interviewee and interviewer were collaborators, making the stories shared by the interviewee meaningful. Learning that when people retell or share their stories, they have the chance to reflect on their actions based on their experiences (Ford, 2021).

Thematic analysis was employed to examine the similarities and differences in their responses regarding the use of AI applications. The following steps for analyzing and decoding data (Caulfield, 2023) were applied:

- Familiarization: Review the collected data. In transcribing the audio/interview, notes were taken, and the data were reviewed before proceeding.
- Coding: Highlighted the sections of the interview; text, phrases, or sentences, then came up with “codes” to describe the content collected.
- Generate themes as the codes created are being reviewed, and similar patterns are identified to help with theme creation.
- Reviewing the themes to check if they were useful and accurately represented the data collected. Reviewing what could be improved.
- Writing up involves writing the analysis from the data gathered. Establishing how the research questions asked reflect the data interpreted, and

- Making sense of the conclusion that explains the takeaways from the analysis and shows how the analysis has answered the research questions.

Open and axial coding were used in the coding process. This method of coding has been advantageous as it provides access to studying the informants' minds, their perspectives, and reactions to the topic (Charmaz, 2008, as cited in Williams & Moser, 2019).

Rigor of the Study

In a qualitative study, rigor refers to the quality of the research as demonstrated by the researchers. This term refers to several strategies that acknowledge the influence of the survey across multiple realities. Dependability is part of the study's consistency, as well as another researcher's ability to achieve the same result using the same process. Credibility, on the other hand, is being confident in the result and the truth of the study's findings. Confirmability refers to the extent to which participants influence the research findings, rather than introducing false data or bias. Lastly, transferability refers to the provision of sufficient information that allows another researcher to verify whether their study is similar and can be applied in their research (Ayton, 2023).

Ethical Considerations

Ethical guidelines were followed to ensure the study participants' privacy, safety, and well-being. Participants' identities were protected, personal information and locations were kept confidential, and all responses were reported anonymously. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were fully aware of the study's purpose and had the right to withdraw. The research questions were

provided beforehand to address any clarifications within the scope of the study before proceeding. While locations and personal identifiers have been omitted, the methodology and findings will be shared transparently, with any limitations acknowledged. These measures were made to ensure the rights and privacy of the participants while still providing meaningful insights and knowledge, as well as additional contributions to the body of knowledge in the name of research.

Chapter 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ten teachers agreed to participate in the interviews conducted from January 28 to 30, 2025. All participants initially experienced teaching without the use of technology, but they gradually adapted to using AI applications. Interviews were recorded for documentation and transcription purposes. The 10 public elementary school teachers were predominantly female (nine out of ten) and one male, reflecting the gendered nature of early-grade teaching in the Philippines. Participants handled a range of grade levels from Kindergarten to Grade 6, with Grade 5 being the most common, taught by four teachers. Two taught Kindergarten, while the remaining participants covered Grades 1, 4, and 6. The teachers' years in service varied widely, providing a balance of perspectives: six teachers had between five and eight years of experience (including one who spent five years in a DepEd office and one year in the classroom), two had eleven years, and two were highly experienced with 31 years of service each. This mix of early-career, mid-career, and veteran teachers provided diverse insights into how digital tools, such as Meta AI and Canva, are communicated with and integrated into instructional practices (Table 1).

Table 1 *Profile of the Elementary School Teachers*

Alias	Grade Handled	Gender	Years in Service
U1	GRADE 1	Female	6 Years
U2	KINDERGARTEN	Female	8 Years
U3	KINDERGARTEN	Female	6 Years
U4	GRADE 5	Female	31 Years
U5	GRADE 6	Female	8 Years

U6	GRADE 4	Female	31 Years
U7	GRADE 5	Male	11 Years
U8	GRADE 6	Female	11 Years
U9	GRADE 5	Female	7 Years
U10	GRADE 5	Female	5 years DepEd Office, 1 year teaching

The following stories provide a glimpse of each teacher's experience, helping better understand their perspective in answering the questions: (1) Why do you use Meta AI and Canva, (2) How do you communicate with Meta AI and Canva, and (3) How do you evaluate the answers/suggestions you get from Meta AI and Canva.

Answers vary, as each person has their way of sharing their story about using these applications.

To ensure the participants' anonymity, they are referred to by their aliases as 'users' or 'U'.

Story of U1

Original Narrative:

"I use Meta AI and Canva for ano rin po para sa mas mabilis na makakuha ng information, so aside from Google mas mabilis rin po kasi makakuha ng mga information sa Meta AI mabilis yung information na maaari mong makuha, sa Canva naman po ginagamit po namin ito sa mga, mga layouts, tulad ng mga poster." (I use Meta AI and Canva to get information faster, aside from Google I could get faster results using Meta AI, and as for Canva I use it for layouts, like posters.)

"Halimbawa tungkol sa "living things" dapat yun isearch mo, parang ano yung theme, parang ganun. Kasi pag wala kang theme na isearch ang dami pong

lumalabas, dami mong options, ang dami mong iscroll, eh kung nagsearch ka ng halimbawa about Math, halimbawa background about “Mathematics for kids” so lalabas na sya dun, kasi pag hindi specific ang dami mong pamimilian dun, pag nagsearch ka po lalabas na yung mga option about dun o yung tema, theme about sa kailangan mo. Ganun po.” (For example, the theme is about “living things.” When you do not have a theme, numerous options are presented; you need to scroll through and select the one that suits you. However, if you search, for example, background in “Mathematics for kids,” it shows. Because when it is not specific, a lot of other options show, but if it has a theme, only the ones you need appear.)

“Ngayon ang bilis, pero syempre naman, yung nakuha mo sa AI ay lahat yun applicable sa, halimbawa magtuturo ka sa bata, syempre iseselect mo, icheck mo din alin yung mas mapapadali, mas mababaw. Kasi syempre usually baka napakalalim na nung mga terminologies mga ano, medyo dapat aanuhin mo. Dapat abot kaya nung mga aanuhan mo.” (Now everything is fast, but of course, the answers get from AI must be applicable. For example, if it is for the students, you should select and check which is easier to understand. Because sometimes the information given has complex terminology, it should be adjusted depending on the student's capacity.)

Restoryed Narrative:

U1 has adapted the use of these AI applications, learning that they have enabled her to be more efficient at her work. Aside from Google's search engine, she shared how she can research information quickly and appreciates Meta AI's swift response. As for Canva, its capability for creating creative poster layouts and offering a variety of options for teachers to use are features that make the application convenient for its users.

Communicating with non-humans was different. There was a restriction on how much it could understand, as conversations could be initiated by typing a prompt. Prompting from U1's point of view should align with the theme. As she shares with creating presentations, this approach is practical because it removes options irrelevant to the task, avoiding unnecessary clutter that is not useful for the task.

With AI applications, getting information faster means understanding to whom this information would be fed. She teaches grade one, and knowing what her students can learn, she selects only ideas and information that are applicable and comprehensible to them. It was not enough to receive the information and suggestions more quickly if the person who needs to understand it cannot comprehend the material being shown. Consideration of the intended learner should be given.

Story of U2

Original Narrative:

“Straight forward na pagtatanong, yung kung anong gusto mong malaman. Kumbaga straight to the point po na, kunwari ang hinahanap nyo po ay ilan ang letters sa alphabet. ‘Di na paligoy ligoy pa. Kasi syempre pag ano pa tayo kung saan pupunta pa...” (Straight to the point question, for example, you are looking for letters of the alphabet, go straight to the point.)

“Binabasa ko sya tapos pinipili ko lang kung alin yung pwede, yung importante, yung pwede kong ilagay sa narrative ko. ‘Di ko sya pwedeng, ano baka tayo maplagiarism pag kinuha ko ng buo yun, kumbaga pinipili ko lang kung alin ang gusto kong kuhanin. Yun yung pag-evaluate ko sa binibigay na sagot ng Meta AI or

ng Canva.” (I choose after reading the generated response. I choose what is important I can use in my narrative. I can’t select all information as it could count as plagiarism, I’ll just choose what I want to use, that’s how I evaluate the answers given by Meta AI or Canva.)

“Yung pinakang simpleng paraan na maiintindihan ng bata yung kukunin namin, yung pag kinuha namin mas mapapadali maintindihan ng mga bata. Dahil ang hawak nyo po ay kinder.” (The simplest way for the children, that’s what I’ll get because I’m handling kindergarten.)

“Ito yun, nilayout ko lang sya sa Canva, ito yung five senses...layout mo lang yan tapos ikaw na ang bahala maggawa. Madami na akong nagawa pero ito yung pinakang-nagamit ko sa pagtuturo ko.” (I made this layout over Canva; it is the five senses... you create a layout, then you can customize it. I have created a lot, but this one is the one I use the most in teaching my class.)

“Syempre bata pa kasi yung learner namin eh, so kailangan nila ng gabay. Gabay ng magulang nila kay Meta AI, Canva naman bata ba sila eh hindi pa pwede. So ano guidance na lang sa paggamit...” (Our learners are still young; they need guidance. Guidance of parents for Meta AI usage and Canva, they are still young to use, so proper guidance is needed.)

Restored Narrative:

As one of the school’s IT staff members, she is the “go-to” person for learning new skills, such as using Canva. Sharing her best practices in prompting these AI applications, she emphasized the importance of being straight to the point when asking. Beating around the bush does not help in acquiring the needed information.

Being aware of the information given by these AI applications helped her evaluate the relevance of each. Selecting essential information and calling attention

to the fact that information should not be copied (plagiarized). Bringing the importance of not plagiarizing other people's work is a good reminder that information provided by Meta AI or Canva is often the idea of others, with corresponding authors. If the task at hand involves writing their narrative, the information generated should serve as a guide to conceptualize their work. Reiterating that AI applications are tools that assist but are not a replacement for human intelligence.

Crafting lessons should align with the student's grasp of the subject matter. Teaching in grade one differs from teaching in higher grades, so choosing and creating materials that engage students of their age should be considered. Customizing the five senses as teaching material became an advantage, as seeing and holding information made learning easier for kindergarten students.

Curiosity is a familiar feeling, but in terms of usage, in U2's mindset, if students are exposed to these AI applications, they should receive proper guidance from their parents. Although they may not yet have the ability to use one at their age, content exposure should still be monitored, as it impacts their view and cognitive development.

Story of U3

Original Narrative:

“Halimbawa dog climbing on the house or ladder, medyo iba kasi yung bigay saken na mga image compared dun sa magsearch ka na lang sa Google, mas maraming variation ka pang makukuha or mas marami pang uhm, ano ito picture na nabibigay saken instead na dun.” (For example, I prompted Meta AI to generate an image of a dog climbing a ladder, but the suggestion given is not what I am really

looking for, unlike when I use Google, where many variations can be seen, unlike using Meta AI.)

“Sa AI may itatanong ka pero di sya specific na masasagot yung tanong mo. Tatanungin ka pa nya kung satisfied ka na ba dun o kung may panibago kang kelangan mo syang replayan ng halimbawa na specific mo dapat yung question mo. For example, yung sa “how to heal sprained ankle,” yung sagot nya saken, di sya ganun ka detailed, kelangan mo pa mag-ask ng another question para maging further or maging specified yung sagot sayo ni Meta.” (Using AI, in my experience sometimes you will not get the answer you are looking for. It would ask if the answer provided is enough. For example, I have asked “how to heal a sprained ankle” but it did not give a complete explanation, I needed to make a follow-up to get further details.)

“Yung di tayo magiging self-reliant tayo sa AI ganun. Ano, ano parin, di ko din masyadong sure, siguro maging mapanuri tayo maging analytic tayo sa nakukuha nating information kasi hindi valid kung yung information na binibigyan saten is yung ay tunay ano.” (We should not be reliant only on using AI. If you are still unsure, be observant and analyze the information received, to validate the information given.)

Restoryed Narrative:

U3's perspective on Meta-AI differs from the other participants in the study, as she seldom uses Meta-AI. She shared a prompt she created: *“dog climbing on the house or ladder.”* She received an unsatisfactory result, not even other variations of what she wanted to see, which set expectations similar to how Google provides suggestions.

She expressed her frustration by not being entirely happy with Meta AI's answer to her queries and having to complete a survey if the received answer was

satisfactory. Google offers more than the short answers she received from Meta AI, suggesting that she believes the application has limitations.

Prompting the application for follow-ups to give more details, she compared Google to her go-to search engine because of how the Google system responds to her query. Google offers a variety of answers and suggestions. Ultimately, it is better than receiving a filtered answer from Meta AI, which sometimes does not provide an exact answer to her query or the suggestion she was expecting.

Aside from the complexities she experienced with using Meta AI, what worries her most in the age of AI is the students' awareness of and ability to use these applications. Claiming the power it holds becomes something that is made easier, but what would then be the point of learning if everything is easy? What if the results of such tools eliminate students' study habits, leading to overreliance on AI?

Story of U4

Original Narrative:

“Dati yung ginagawa ko ng ilang oras, siguro mga two hours, three hours. Ngayon kayang kaya mong gawin, ngayon mga wala pang 1 minute, isang click lang, siguro mga one-minute pag clinick mo pero ano ayan na. Diretso na.” (Before, it would take me two hours or three hours to finish the schoolworks, but now it can be done in a minute.)

“...’Di na ako nahihirapan, isang click mo lamang nandito na yung letter o kaya, make me a lesson plan. Papagawa din ako sa kanya ng lesson plan na tungkol sa adverb o kaya about verb. O sa math, pagbukas mo noon kumpleto na, hindi na ako mag-iisip madali na lang pala netong AI na ito. Parang pinadali yung buhay ko.” (I am no longer burdened; with one click, the answer is like a letter, or

like when I ask to create a lesson plan.) Sometimes I prompt the AI to create a lesson plan about an adverb or verb. Even in math, when I review the material generated by the application, the information I need is complete; I do not even need to think about what to create, as the AI makes it easier. AI made my life easier.)

“Oo nagagamit ko sya, halimbawa, yung sa anak ko, minsan nag-away kami ng anak ko. ‘Di naman nag-away, kumbaga di ko lang sya naintindihan. “How to deal with teenagers?” Ganyan kasi teenager na yung anak ko.” (I have used it, for example, when my child and I have a misunderstanding. I search “how to deal with teenagers” as my child is already in their teen years.)

Restoryed Narrative:

U4 can now receive sufficient support as Meta AI and Canva have helped alleviate the burden of creating lessons, presentations, and teaching materials. She shared that she would sacrifice two to three hours to finish her task before, but now, developing or looking for information has been as easy as a mouse click. She felt relieved because AI applications have allowed her to expedite her task. With applications like Meta AI and Canva existing, it took half the time to complete the tasks.

PowerPoint presentations are advantageous, from brainstorming ideas for her lessons per subject to typing a prompt and asking to generate documents. She reiterated that these applications made her work life easier. Apart from using the application in teaching, she recalled instances where she had used Meta AI to ask questions that helped improve her relationship with her daughter. She mentioned the times she and her daughter had misunderstandings, and she asked Meta AI to help her have better conversations. Seeking advice from Meta AI to improve her communication and better relate to her daughter.

Story of U5

Original Narrative:

“Oo, kumbaga minsan hindi lang ako once nagtype nung information na gusto kong makita. Minsan medyo iniiba ko din, kasi tinitingnan ko din ano pa yung ibang information na ibibigay saken nung AI.” (Yes, sometimes I retype the information I wanted to see. I change it a little, just to check what other information that AI could give.)

“Kasi nga kahit sa internet, sa internet o sa ibang mga site so minsan may mga information din tayo na mapapaisip tayo kung ito ba ay reliable or hindi. Nagkakaroon pa tayo ng comparison. Titingin tayo sa isang pinagkukunan ng information sa isa pang pinagkukunan ng information, parang kung alin dun yung mas pinakamadami na most the same ang sinasabi e di yun yung information na kukunin.” (Even on the internet there is information where you will think twice if it is reliable or not, for that we go to other search engine then we can compare information, information that has the most similarities should be the one chosen.)

“Kasi ang dali ang bilis, kumbaga isang type mo lang pag meron kang gustong makuhang info, makukuha mo. Kahit nga yung sample Daily Lesson Log (DLL) or lesson plan ng teacher eh may lumalabas na information. Sample yung co-teacher ko sa math kasi may time na kumbaga ay lack of ah sabihin na nating nagkulang kami ng activities sa bata kumbaga nakapagbigay na kami ng drill 1, drill 2, or activity 1 and activity 2, na kinulang kami so halimbawa ganun makakapag-add ka ng gawain or pwede pang activities sa kanila with the use of AI.” (It’s easy and fast, with just a click away you can get the information you need, even sample Daily Lesson Log (DLL) or lesson plans. Like the time my co-teacher in math lacks activities to carry out, we can add more activities and ask for advice using AI.)

Restoryed Narrative:

Strategy is essential in creating AI prompts. In U5's case, her curiosity led her to improve the prompts she creates to achieve the correct answer. As a grade six teacher, she is very observant and promotes quality checks for the information obtained online to mitigate misinformation. She believes it is better to stay vigilant and verify the information being shared and used; checking the source is an effective way to determine if the information is legitimate.

She shared that to get the best answer, she tweaked her prompts to check how similar or different the generated responses were from those coming from the application. These AI applications were introduced by overhearing her co-teachers who used them for their Daily Lesson Logs. From brainstorming ideas to completing activities to share with their students, the apps helped them generate ideas and create sample quizzes. They acted like an extension of the teacher, having a second brain that helped with their work.

Story of U6

Original Narrative:

"...kasi ano kesa hanap ka sa books, sa iba-iba pang books e di dun ka na lang magtanong sa AI, tapos pag may doubt ka tsaka ka na lang magtitingin dun sa books, kung mali ba o tama yun. 'Di katulad dati na pag magtuturo ka ang dami mong reference books na tinitingnan. Tapos pag ano iba-iba pa yung information na nandun kasi nga mga ano di updated, may times na mga books ko ng elementary nagagamit ko, na kumbaga nagiging guide mo pa din eh kumbaga elementary ka pa books na sya, outdated na." (Rather than looking at different books, I will ask AI. If you have doubts about the information, you will need to verify it through books to

determine its accuracy. Back then, before I could teach, I needed to check all the information from textbooks. At times I even use the books I used when I was in elementary, but it is worrisome since textbooks published when I was still in elementary school may already be outdated.)

“Meron din clarification na totoo ba yung sagot kasi parang nagdadoubt ako sa sagot na totoo ba ito, parang mali ata yung sagot neto sa tanong ko. Ang ginagawa ko pag may doubt pa-follow up, parang may doubt ka pa rin e di sa ibang apps ka na lang o kaya ay sa books, izearch mo na lang sa books para kung tama ba yung sagot din.” (There is clarification as well if the answer is correct. At times I doubt its correctness, so I make follow up questions. If I still have doubts, I use other apps or check on books whether the answer is right.)

“Pag mas madali kasi tatanggapin ko, kasi mas madali na yung application nya eh, pagka mahirap kasi pag ang daming mga pag madami ka pang ilalagay sa application sa program na sinuggest nya, di ko gagawin yun, dun na ako sa may madali, kesa dun sa mahirap. Kumbaga ano madami siyang design, pipili ako ng simpleng design na madali kong mababago, kesa dun sa design na madami kang aayusin. (If it is easier I will accept it, but if the application is difficult to navigate and requires a lot of input in the program as it suggests then I will not use it. If the app has different options, I will choose something that I can simply use rather than something that is complicated.)

“Madaling maaccess yung dalawa, yung Meta AI, pag may mga questions asked ka, madaling sumagot. Yung Canva naman magagamit mo sya pag gagawa ng PowerPoint presentation, sa akin ah ginagamit ko sya sa powerpoint presentation. Mga paggagawa lang na yun nga, program, yun ganun lang.” (Both

applications are easy to access. Meta AI helped me with quick inquiries, while I used canva for my presentations. These applications helped me create programs.)

Restoryed Narrative:

U6's teaching experience involved utilizing a wide range of reference materials. She shared how she stacked books in front of her to get information for creating her lessons. She remembered even using books of the same age as her own as resource material for her students, as these were the few she could rely on to provide the information she needed to teach the lesson. She saw how difficult it is to update current information as materials are limited to none. With the advent of AI, many aspects of life have undergone significant changes.

The use of the application came with the doubt that the information generated might be incorrect, as it was still new and the developers were learning, and having doubts was normal. Regarding this mindset, obtaining follow-ups to clarify was the right approach, but if uncertainty persisted, seeking alternative applications or consulting books should still be an option. There is nothing wrong with seeking clarification, as it benefited her and the class she taught; it assured her that the content presented needed to be validated because the students relied on their teachers for knowledge.

U6 shared that she learned something in teaching: Students learned better if the lessons were not presented in a complicated way. As a non-technical person, she applied this approach when creating presentations, as the content mattered more than the design. Convenience in access and navigation was a key factor in wanting to utilize the application, as it provided fast responses, made it easy to create presentations, and ultimately made Meta AI and Canva something U6 wanted to use.

Story of U7

Original Narrative:

“Pwede ng gumawa ng videos sa Canva may mga ready-made na silang mga template dun gagamitin mo na lang kumbaga ah tawag dito lagay ka na lang ng lagay ng mga pictures tapos iaayos mo na lang then ikaw na yung bahalang mag animations, ganun kaya kumbaga yung tools na yan hanggang ngayon now ginagamit ko pa din sa pagtuturo. Wala ako ditong maiaano sayo eh yung kahit sa mga school yung ID ng bata yun sa Canva din namin.” (You can make videos in Canva as there are ready-made templates that can be used and it’s up to you to customize and animate. That’s the reason why even now I use Canva for teaching. Even our students ID is made from Canva.)

“Meta AI kasi when it comes to lesson na kailangan mong magresearch kumbaga para magkaroon ka din ng review or deep understanding dun sa lesson na gusto mong ituro sa bata para mas lalo silang makainteract malaking tulong din, maganda oo.” (Meta AI is beneficial when it comes to researching lessons, so I can review and have a deep understanding of the lesson I want to teach, so that I can interact with the students better. Meta AI is excellent; it is a big help.)

“Ginagamit namin sa teachers guide kumbaga ano naman sya kumbaga wala naman syang discrepancy, kumbaga parehas din naman sya mas kumbaga ano advance lang yung knowledge na makukuha kay Meta AI.” (Teachers, based on the teachers’ guide, if there is no discrepancy with the lesson and the information searched from Meta AI is similar, then there should not be any problem; Meta AI provides additional advanced information.)

Restoryed Narrative:

U7 is a proud user of Canva. He explained that videos can be added to the slides, highlighting the application's personalization feature in addition to creating static presentations. Expressing his amazement with Canva, he encouraged its use, even with the students' school IDs, which were created on Canva. From the first time learning the application to mastering its utilization, Canva has significantly changed how it creates teaching materials.

Aside from creating his lessons, he used Meta AI to learn from them, as the application acts as his teacher. Pointing out that having a more engaging discussion with his students and gaining a deeper understanding of the lesson was his way of preparing. If he is knowledgeable about the lesson, he can adjust how to relay it to his students so that they can grasp and learn the lesson more effectively. This also enhanced the skill of communicating with AI.

He continues to use the applications because there were no discrepancies between the lessons and the AI-generated information. This raises a green flag that technology and advances like AI should be utilized.

Story of U8

Original Narrative:

“...mas madali na kasi mas less na yung ano, yung time na gugugulin mo paggawa ng slide, kagaya nga nung sinasabi ko na, dati pipili ka ng magandang background, font size, o kaya yung image na iinsert. Nandoon sa Canva, talagang mas eksakto mo halimbawa yung sa Science, Values, yung may specific topic.” (... it is easier, I spent less time creating slides. Before, it was a hassle when I needed a background for my presentation, from choosing fonts to getting images. In Canva,

everything is exact. For example, for Science or Values, there are options for a specific topic.)

“...kagaya neto may hindi magandang incident ng sa page yung away, kaya lang di nagamit sa magandang paraan yung sa binasa mo yung respond kasi may specific topic silang di pinagkakaintindihan mapapansin mo sa sagot na generated lang, di gawa ng bata. Yun ang di maganda dun.” (...there was an incident concerning a student quarrel on an online group page. AI was used to provide an answer, but it was used for a negative purpose. There was a topic that they fought over; anyone can notice it was AI-generated and not written by a child. That is not good.)

Restoryed Narrative:

U8 felt she was not alone, as AI applications exist. Accomplishing tasks helped her speed up the process, and she spent less time thinking as the application could think for her. Creating instructional materials became easy, as options were available in Canva. She mentioned just prompting what she needed, and the application provided what was available. Knowing what kind of background, font, or image to include was no longer a worry for her, as there were choices that made it easy for her to make a selection.

Her concern about AI utilization is centered on how students learn to use it, rather than for academic purposes. She shared an incident where a student was criticized online for commenting on a post using AI, which led to a disagreement. This emphasizes that AI usage has both positive and negative traits, depending on who uses it and for what purpose.

Story of U9

Original Narrative:

“Sobrang laki syempre kasi ngayon ano ka na lang type ka na lang ng idea mo type mo lang di ba. Kunwari sa encyclopedia hahanapin mo pa yung letter di ba meron tayong set ng encyclopedia hahanapin mo pa yung letter kung ano yung naisip mong hanapin di ba ganun po. Kaya saken sobrang laki ng impact ng technology kumbaga sa atin yung mga ganyan, syempre mas napadali.” (It has a great impact, because now you can type your ideas. Before, we use books like encyclopedias to search for a particular word. So, for me the impact of technology, it made things easier.)

“Ito yung estudyante ko may gamot yung baby ko na natira tapos meron sugat yung estudyante ko, sinearch ko pwede ba yung gamot na yun sa gantong ano, gantong skin ano nya allergy nya. Kasi yung anak ko nagka-allergy tapos sinearch ko kung pwede kasi wala daw syang gamot eh, yun tiningnan ko kung pwede. Maibibigay naman nila yung detail ano eh.” (My baby has excess allergy medication. I have searched to see if the medicine can be used for a particular allergy, in case it could be used by my student for their wound. Details are given when searched in Meta AI.)

“...halimbawa may gusto akong, kunyari gusto kong maggawa ng certificate, search ko lang dun kunwari pang sports certificate yung ano yung pang honors namin sa mga bata yung mga pang achiever mga ganan. Isearch mo lang yun magbibigay na sila ng mga ano eh, ng mga set na pamimilian mo. Maganda sya.”

(For example, if I wanted to do a certificate, I would search for sports certificates for honors for our students who are achievers. When searched it gave options. It's great!)

“Ano lang din, hindi ako fully syempre ano kasi nga yung natanong ko ay gamot e di syempre nakalagay dun sabi ni Meta AI para mas sure ka kailangan mo mag ano sa doctor. Ayun nakalagay naman dun, parang meron silang mga reminder. Parang may ano sila.” (For me I do not fully accept, because my question is about medication and as indicated by Meta AI as a disclaimer for assurance I need to check with a doctor.)

“Kukuha lang akong idea, kaya pag ano sasabihin saken ni Doc nung first na bagong bago pa lang akong mommy parang mga 4 months 6 months e di nagtanong ako kay Doc sabi ko “Doc bawal po bang uminom ng uminom pa ng water yung baby? Milk pa lang?” Sabi nya saan mo nalaman yun Ginoogle mo yan no sabi nung pedia ng baby ko. Kasi parang ano nga sinearch ko, pwede na bang uminom ng gantong months na baby.” (I just want to get an idea, I was a first-time mom around 4 to 6 months when I asked, “Doc can the baby drink water? Or Milk only?” then the Doctor commented on where I got the information and if it is in Google. It’s because at the time I did the research about if the baby could already drink water within these months.)

Restoryed Narrative:

U9 showed interest in using Meta AI and Canva because she related how different and easier it was to conduct research now compared to before. Allotting time to find references and information in books used to take much time, unlike now, when getting information online is easy and fast. It brought significant changes to how things work.

Sharing an instance where she used Meta AI to ask for medical advice, giving her answers that could help her student. This highlights the fact that these AI applications are adaptable to those using them, as they are knowledgeable about

other information and are not limited to academic purposes. It highlighted what AI applications are: tools used to assist humans.

Appropriately prompting AI gave promising results, but U9 was still in awe of how practical these AI applications are. The study showed that familiarity with demonstrations can yield different results depending on how the prompt was created.

Story of U10

Original Narrative:

“Nung time na nung time na ano pa lang, wala pa yung mga ganyang technology talagang mahirap kasi lahat gagawin mo pasulat. Gagawa ka ng ano isusulat mo, visual aids, kailangan mo mag gupit o magdrawing then nung dumating itong mga technology natin kay Canva madali na magpresent ng picture. Mapagsasama sama mo sya sa isang page lang.... ngayon na dumating din itong si AI Meta kumbaga yung mga behind question na hindi mo agad masasagot na kailangan mong magresearch iclick mo lang kay AI ayan na may result ka kaagad. Yun yung kagandahan ng technology natin ngayon kay Canva tsaka sa ayan.” (The time when we did not have that technology, it was difficult because all work needs to be handwritten. For visual aids you need cutouts or drawing, but with technology like Canva, now you can present a picture, collage and put it in one page. As for Meta AI, your questions could be answered in one click.)

“In terms of sa work oo ang laking tulong ni AI pero in terms naman na pinag-aanuhan ng bata diba kinacater namin bata...kung yung mga bata ay aasa na lang kay AI wala na yung ano wala na yung study habit ng bata kasi ‘iclick ko na lang dito alam na yan ni Meta yung sagot’ so maisusulat man nila walang mareretain sa mind

ng bata yun yung magiging disadvantage ng technology sa bata.” (In work, AI is beneficial, but for kids, if they rely entirely on AI, their study habits could disappear because everything is one click away from Meta AI generating an answer. Even if they wrote it down, they would not retain the information, and this would be a disadvantage of technology for the kids.)

“Yan na yung papasok na yung part ng teacher tsaka yung magulang na lagi sila magkateam up, di pwedeng lagi si teacher lang kasi samin ilang oras lang si bata pagdating sa bahay. Pagdating sa bahay mas malaki yung oras ng magulang na dapat nasusubaybayan nila, so dapat magkakaran ng team-up si teacher atsaka si parent para bigyan ng limited time ng nasa bahay for gadget then tuturuan mo din sya kahit paano sa libro magbasa di puro AI. Kumbaga ituro kay bata na icompare si books tsaka si AI, ano yung magiging impact sa bata ganun din ang gagawin sa school. So, para hindi mawala yung study habit ng bata kailangan sa bahay at sa school may ginagawa sila.” (That's where the teacher and parent team-up, as the child only is with us a few hours unlike at home. Kids spend a lot more time at home so the parents should monitor the kids. They could give rules for limiting gadget usage and encourage them to read books. Let the kids compare books and AI, see the impact, and apply it at school, so that their study habits will not disappear.)

Restoryed Narrative:

Recalling how difficult it was back then, U10 shared her experience of putting in much effort to prepare her teaching materials. Everything was manual, from writing titles for visual aids to cutting out her drawings. It required considerable manual labor, from gathering answers to questions to preparing reports. Time management played a crucial role in her ability to accomplish everything she set out to do. Still, it all changed when applications like Meta AI and Canva emerged,

allowing her to transition from trying to perfect her penmanship and drawings to creating with drag-and-drop options that fit all the necessary information on one page. This is an advancement no one could overlook.

In terms of its use in her line of work, she found that AI was helpful, but she expressed reservations about students using the application, as she worries that they might end up relying on AI for their education. She believed that the development of students' comprehension, problem-solving, and rationality should be emphasized because knowledge retention is crucial. The advantage of AI to the teacher might become a disadvantage to the students.

Looking at it, she knew she could not do anything to prevent students from using AI, so she suggested that teachers and parents act as a team to regulate how students use the application, while not entirely giving up the traditional way of using books in learning, to check the impact of both methods on the students. If AI is here to stay, it is highly recommended that we explore ways to utilize it.

Themes Identified

Based on these narratives, four interconnected topics were drawn: (1) Communicating with Meta AI and Canva, (2) Workflow Shift (Meta AI and Canva Usage), (3) Skepticism with AI Communication, and (4) AI's Perceived Identity (Who is AI?). By narrative inquiry, diverse perspectives have been accumulated. Each was represented by themes that emerged from the participants' lived experiences.

Communicating with Meta AI and Canva

Theme 1: Prompt Crafting Process

Meta AI is still new and learning; using clear and non-complex commands can benefit from the application's generated responses. Using keywords helps

distinguish and frame the prompt better. According to Merriam-Webster (n.d.), this definition involves using a significant word from a title to index content.

Communicating with AI applications is not the same as conversing with humans who understand gestures, pauses, tones, or humor. Learning to craft effective prompts leads to satisfactory results. Participants shared their best practice vetted on being transparent and straightforward with creating the prompt, like the following excerpt:

U2 narrates, ““Straight forward na pagtatanong, yung kung anong gusto mong malaman. Kumbaga straight to the point po na, kunwari ang hinahanap nyo po ay ilan ang letters sa alphabet. ‘Di na paligoy ligoy pa. Kasi syempre pag ano pa tayo kung saan pupunta pa...” (Straight to the point question, for example, you are looking for letters of the alphabet, go straight to the point.)

Knowing what information she needed made prompting the application easy, as she expected to receive what she requested.

U1, on the other hand, explained further instructions on how she created her prompt:

“Halimbawa tungkol sa “living things” dapat yun isearch mo, parang ano yung theme, parang ganun. Kasi pag wala kang theme na isearch ang dami pong lumalabas, dami mong options, ang dami mong iscroll, eh kung nagsearch ka ng halimbawa about Math, halimbawa background about “Mathematics for kids” so lalabas na sya dun, kasi pag hindi specific ang dami mong pamimilian dun, pag nagsearch ka po lalabas na yung mga option about dun o yung tema, theme about sa kailangan mo. Ganun po.” (For example, the theme is about “living things.” When you do not have a theme, numerous options are presented; you need to scroll through and select the one that suits you. However, if you search, for example,

background in “Mathematics for kids,” it shows. Because when it is not specific, a lot of other options show, but if it has a theme, only the ones you need appear.)

Providing the necessary information leads to obtaining what is needed. Including relevant information in crafting the prompt was relevant, as per U1. U9 agreed and shares the same mindset when prompted to apply. For instance:

“...halimbawa may gusto akong, kunyari gusto kong maggawa ng certificate, search ko lang dun kunwari pang sports certificate yung ano yung pang honors namin sa mga bata yung mga pang achiever mga ganan. Isearch mo lang yun magbibigay na sila ng mga ano eh, ng mga set na pamimilian mo. Maganda sya.”

(For example, if I wanted to do a certificate, I would search for sports certificates for honors for our students who are achievers. When searched it gave options. It is great!)

This method promotes efficiency in finishing the task and filters out unnecessary information/answers. AI applications rely entirely on the prompts created for them to respond; well-written commands enable them to process the question more effectively and generate the closest answer to the inquiry sent to them.

Responses given by AI applications largely depended on the prompt, whereas their usefulness and correctness relied on what was being asked. The relevance of the prompt is important as it impacts the quality of the answer that the AI application would provide to its user, as experienced by U2:

“Binabasa ko sya tapos pinipili ko lang kung alin yung pwede, yung importante, yung pwede kong ilagay sa narrative ko. ‘Di ko sya pwedeng, ano baka tayo maplagiarism pag kinuha ko ng buo yun, kumbaga pinipili ko lang kung alin ang gusto kong kuhanin. Yun yung pag-evaluate ko sa binibigay na sagot ng Meta AI or

ng Canva.” (I choose after reading the generated response. I choose what is important I can use in my narrative. I cannot select all information as it could count as plagiarism, I will just choose what I want to use, that’s how I evaluate the answers given by Meta AI or Canva.)

From U2’s perspective, even if these applications gave several suggestions or categorized answers, she only got what she needed. She was careful when creating her prompt to get accurate answers, because even if the information were deemed correct, she would disregard it if it did not fit the criteria/topic she needed it for.

Theme 2: Consideration and Relatability

For U1’s advice, she believed that including other factors, such as age, would yield better answers. As an elementary teacher, creating a prompt that considered the intended learners gave her an advantage in determining what to include to elicit applicable information. She shared:

“It needs to fit the criteria, *“Ngayon ang bilis, pero syempre naman, yung nakuha mo sa AI ay lahat yun applicable sa, halimbawa magtuturo ka sa bata, syempre iseselect mo, icheck mo din alin yung mas mapapadali, mas mababaw. Kasi syempre usually baka napakalalim na nung mga terminologies mga ano, medyo dapat aanuhin mo. Dapat abot kaya nung mga aanuhan mo.”* (Now everything is fast, but of course, the answers get from AI must be applicable. For example, if it is for the students, you should select and check which is easier to understand. Because sometimes the information given has complex terminology, it should be adjusted depending on the student's capacity.)

This helps avoid miscommunication and receive applicable, generated responses that are favorable to the user’s intention, which optimizes results. From

another perspective, U6 shared her methods for accepting or rejecting AI-generated information/suggestions. As a non-techie, U6 admitted that she would choose the easy option based on the application's suggestion, such as:

“Pag mas madali kasi tatanggapin ko, kasi mas madali na yung application nya eh, pagka mahirap kasi pag ang daming mga pag madami ka pang ilalagay sa application sa program na sinuggest nya, di ko gagawin yun, dun na ako sa may madali, kesa dun sa mahirap. Kumbaga ano madami siyang design, pipili ako ng simpleng design na madali kong mababago, kesa dun sa design na madami kang aayusin.” (If it is easier I will accept it, but if the application is difficult to navigate and requires a lot of input in the program as it suggests then I will not use it. If the app has different options, I will choose something that I can simply use rather than something that is complicated.)

Adding to her stance on this matter was U2's perspective that choosing which to accept or reject came with the question *“who is it for?”*

“Yung pinakang simpleng paraan na maiintindihan ng bata yung kukunin namin, yung pag kinuha namin mas mapapadali maintindihan ng mga bata. Dahil ang hawak nyo po ay kinder.” (The simplest way for the children, that's what I'll get because I'm handling kindergarten.)

Furthermore, she said *“Ito yun, nilayout ko lang sya sa Canva, ito yung five senses...layout mo lang yan tapos ikaw na ang bahala maggawa. Madami na akong nagawa pero ito yung pinakang-nagamit ko sa pagtuturo ko.”* (I created this layout using Canva, which is based on the five senses. You create a layout, and then you can customize it. I have created many layouts, but this one is the one I use most often in my class.)

In the communication process between humans and AI, several factors should be considered; a well-written, non-complex, and clear prompt would yield exemplary results. This incentivized users to construct commands that conveyed a complete thought, filtering out unnecessary information that could lead to confusion in the application and result in incorrect data.

This shows that when communicating with machines, it guides humans to communicate a complete thought, unlike when humans communicate with another person. In human-to-human conversation, there are instances where the other person shows subtle gesture cues, speaks with a different tone of voice, and engages in the conversation with incomplete sentences, or even uses figurative language and humor. However, the other person in the conversation can still understand the information shared. The construct of meaning-making and information exchange differs when interacting with machines, as humans are obliged to communicate in a certain way (prompting) to gain information.

Exchange of information would only occur once a prompt is sent into the AI application's system. In human communication, there are more ways to convey the information one has in mind. The similarities and differences in processes indicate that, in the digital era of communication with AI, aside from new ways of obtaining information, acknowledging and embodying a change in behavior is necessary to communicate better.

In relation to the teachers' prompting the application, they have their reasons and explanations for how they prompt the application, as they must remember and consider who it is for, what information is needed, and how to present the information to their students.

While the communication process may differ in a digital environment, the essential requirements for effective teaching — clear goals, intentional practice, and learner-centered design — remain unchanged. Teaching practices now combine traditional and digital methods, with the shared goal of improving educational quality. Similarly, users must be trained to prompt AI tools effectively, much like training in any pedagogical method. Over time, AI systems can adapt to users' unique styles and needs, enabling the creation of more personalized and collaborative knowledge and instructional materials.

Workflow Shift (Meta AI and Canva Usage)

Theme 1: Instantly Generated Results

Most of the teachers conveyed their delight in using Meta AI and Canva in their work, as U1 shared her experience of how the application made her workload easier:

“I use Meta AI and Canva for ano rin po para sa mas mabilis na makakuha ng information, so aside from Google mas mabilis rin po kasi makakuha ng mga information sa Meta AI mabilis yung information na maaari mong makuha, sa Canva naman po ginagamit po namin ito sa mga, mga layouts, tulad ng mga poster.” (I use Meta AI and Canva to get information faster, aside from Google I could get faster results using Meta AI, and as for Canva I use it for layouts, like posters)

Her fast and informative response to how the application made her feel revealed how practical it has been. Her co-teacher, U4, shared the same sentiments about how the application helped her speed up her tasks.

U4's shared *“Dati yung ginagawa ko ng ilang oras, siguro mga two hours, three hours. Ngayon kayang kaya mong gawin, ngayon mga wala pang 1 minute,*

isang click lang, siguro mga one-minute pag clinick mo pero ano ayan na. Diretso na.” (Before, it would take me two hours or three hours to finish the schoolworks, but now it can be done in a minute.)

Continuing she says, “...*'Di na ako nahihirapan, isang click mo lamang nandito na yung letter o kaya, make me a lesson plan. Papagawa din ako sa kanya ng lesson plan na tungkol sa adverb o kaya about verb. O sa math, pagbukas mo noon kumpleto na, hindi na ako mag-iisip madali na lang pala netong AI na ito. Parang pinadali yung buhay ko.*” (I am no longer burdened; with one click, the answer appears like a letter, or when I ask to create a lesson plan.) Sometimes I prompt AI to make a lesson plan about an adverb or a verb. Even in math, when I review the material generated by the application, the information I need is complete; I do not even need to think about what to create. AI makes it easier. AI made my life easier.)

U4, with 31 years of experience in teaching, grasped both ends. She experienced teaching the traditional way, where everything was manual, but times have changed as applications like Meta AI and Canva have become significant.

On U5's part she opened her experience with: “*Kasi ang dali ang bilis, kumbaga isang type mo lang pag meron kang gustong makuhang info, makukuha mo. Kahit nga yung sample Daily Lesson Log (DLL) or lesson plan ng teacher eh may lumalabas na information. Sample yung co-teacher ko sa math kasi may time na kumbaga ay lack of ah sabihin na nating nagkulang kami ng activities sa bata kumbaga nakapagbigay na kami ng drill 1, drill 2, or activity 1 and activity 2, na kinulang kami so halimbawa ganun makakapag-add ka ng gawain or pwede pang activities sa kanila with the use of AI.*” (It's easy and fast, with just a click away you can get the information you need, even sample Daily Lesson Log (DLL) or lesson

plans. Like the time my co-teacher in math lacks activities to carry out, we can add more activities and ask for advice using AI.)

U5's narrative highlighted the application's usefulness, as it can produce answers, ideas, and even material that would not have been possible before. In U6's end, she promoted how accessible the application was:

“Madaling maaccess yung dalawa, yung Meta AI, pag may mga questions asked ka, madaling sumagot. Yung Canva naman magagamit mo sya pag gagawa ng PowerPoint presentation, sa akin ah ginagamit ko sya sa powerpoint presentation. Mga paggagawa lang na yun nga, program, yun ganun lang.” (Both applications are easy to access. Meta AI helped me with quick inquiries, while I used Canva for my presentations. These applications helped me create programs.)

Identifying how the application brought significant changes in how they do things, and how these AI apps can be used for different tasks, hastened the teacher's teaching and learning process. Regarding U7's feedback, the outcomes included continued usage and becoming a loyal user. Learning that the application aligned with the teacher's guide, he became comfortable using Meta AI and Canva:

“Ginagamit namin sa teachers guide kumbaga ano naman sya kumbaga wala naman syang discrepancy, kumbaga parehas din naman sya mas kumbaga ano advance lang yung knowledge na makukuha kay Meta AI.” (Teachers, based on the teachers' guide, if there is no discrepancy with the lesson and the information searched from Meta AI is similar, then there should not be any problem. Meta AI gives other advanced information.)

Sharing also *“Pwede ng gumawa ng videos sa Canva may mga ready-made na silang mga template dun gagamitin mo na lang kumbaga ah tawag dito lagay ka na lang ng lagay ng mga pictures tapos iaayos mo na lang then ikaw na yung*

bahalang mag animations, ganun kaya kumbaga yung tools na yan hanggang ngayon now ginagamit ko pa din sa pagtuturo. Wala ako ditong maiaano sayo eh yung kahit sa mga school yung ID ng bata yun sa Canva din namin.” (You can make videos in Canva as there are ready-made templates that can be used, and it is up to you to customize and animate. That is the reason even now I use Canva for teaching. Even our students ID is made from Canva.)

His respect for the application was different. In his interview, he revealed that, besides creating instructional materials, he used the application to educate himself, which is aptly described:

“Meta AI kasi when it comes to lesson na kailangan mong magresearch kumbaga para magkaroon ka din ng review or deep understanding dun sa lesson na gusto mong ituro sa bata para mas lalo silang makainteract malaking tulong din, maganda oo.” (Meta AI is beneficial when it comes to researching lessons, so I can review and have a deep understanding of the lesson I want to teach, so that I can interact with the students better. Meta AI is excellent; it is a big help.)

Instantly receiving information is a game-changer in research and teaching, as it allows teachers to conduct research more efficiently and effectively, as more resources can be identified and utilized. Gone are the days when they would settle for the books they own, the published reading materials from the library, or outdated resources, as there are no other materials available. Now, actions enable research to be conducted more quickly and efficiently.

The stress of finding the right resource is gone, as AI applications can assist teachers in locating what they need. Working more hours than needed, losing sleep to comply with the required materials from reports, visual aids, and lesson plans, is a thing of the past. The quality of teaching falters if the teacher cannot manage the

requirements. It is not that they could not but teachers are human as well, putting pressure on them with ensuring they are going beyond what are expected from them is not a badge of honor to flash so they could be acknowledged that they are good teachers, their level of exhaustion does not need to equate that as educators they are expected to work longer hours to create exceptional teaching materials.

If AI applications can help ease the burden, then using the application should be the least of their worries. AI applications will benefit both teachers and students, as teachers can create more effective lessons (by developing better materials and designing more challenging and engaging lessons), and students can gain more informative and valuable lessons with updated content and learning opportunities.

Theme 2: Traditional to Digital (Merge of Methods)

Shifting from traditional to digital is a huge step, as it promotes new ways of getting information and creating lessons. With the advent of the internet, numerous opportunities emerged in various fields. Up until recently, advancements like AI have been popular, revolutionizing the future with technology that enables the assistance of AI applications, automates small administrative tasks, generates information when prompted, and suggests designs with just a click away. An application was made accessible to the public, like Meta AI and Canva. Having features that bridge human and machine communication, forming a bond that allows the collaborative process of information exchange.

Human-computer interaction is closely tied to AI. While HCI focuses on the interface of computers and their design usability, AI helps by understanding how humans interact, as it mimics human knowledge and behavior. This helps HCI

understand why certain products are more effective. HCI aims to create user-centered design (Sadiku et al., 2021).

HCI helps design its systems intuitively, resulting in users, such as teachers or even students, interacting with the applications easily and engagingly. For example, Meta AI adjusts to communicate effectively at the user's pace, as it can personalize or adapt to the user's pace and style. Similarly, Canva has user-friendly drag-and-drop functions. HCI focuses on ensuring that users can use the tools efficiently. These features and advancements differentiate how teachers currently develop their lessons.

U9 shared the difficulty of doing research before:

“Sobrang laki syempre kasi ngayon ano ka na lang type ka na lang ng idea mo type mo lang di ba. Kunwari sa encyclopedia hahanapin mo pa yung letter di ba meron tayong set ng encyclopedia hahanapin mo pa yung letter kung ano yung naiisip mong hanapin di ba ganun po. Kaya saken sobrang laki ng impact ng technology kumbaga sa atin yung mga ganyan, syempre mas napadali.” (It has a great impact, because now you can type your ideas. Before, we use books like encyclopedias to search for a particular word. So, for me the impact of technology, it made things easier.)

U10 came with her side with the same point of view:

“Nung time na nung time na ano pa lang, wala pa yung mga ganyang technology talagang mahirap kasi lahat gagawin mo pasulat. Gagawa ka ng ano isusulat mo, visual aids, kailangan mo mag gupit o magdrawing then nung dumating itong mga technology natin kay Canva madali na magpresent ng picture. Mapagsasama sama mo sya sa isang page lang.... ngayon na dumating din itong si AI Meta kumbaga yung mga behind question na hindi mo agad masasagot na

kailangan mong magresearch iclick mo lang kay AI ayon na may result ka kaagad. Yun yung kagandahan ng technology natin ngayon kay Canva tsaka sa ayon.” (The time when we did not have that technology, it was difficult because all work needs to be handwritten. For visual aids you need cutouts or drawing, but with technology like Canva, now you can present a picture, collage and put it in one page. As for Meta AI, your questions could be answered in one click.)

AI advancements made a difference. The applications uncover the qualities that would not have been possible in any AI environment. Reducing mistakes, personalizing materials, and offering options for editing what has been created. U8 saw these opportunities to hide that she is not as inclined as the others in design and the arts:

“...mas madali na kasi mas less na yung ano, yung time na gugugulin mo paggawa ng slide, kagaya nga nung sinasabi ko na, dati pipili ka ng magandang background, font size, o kaya yung image na iinsert. Nandoon sa Canva, talagang mas eksakto mo halimbawa yung sa Science, Values, yung may specific topic.” (... it is easier, I spent less time creating slides. Before, it was a hassle when I needed a background for my presentation, from choosing fonts to getting images. In Canva, everything is exact. For example, for Science or Values, there are options for a specific topic.)

Apart from the skills-wise assistance, getting the latest information from the generated information has been the best upgrade an educator would request. U6 is relieved to know that the information she is teaching and sharing with her students is up to date with valid resources, which is one of the reasons she utilizes the applications:

U6 narrated, "...kasi ano kesa hanap ka sa books, sa iba-iba pang books e di dun ka na lang magtanong sa AI, tapos pag may doubt ka tsaka ka na lang magtitingin dun sa books, kung mali ba o tama yun. 'Di katulad dati na pag magtuturo ka ang dami mong reference books na tinitingnan. Tapos pag ano iba-iba pa yung information na nandun kasi nga mga ano di updated, may times na mga books ko ng elementary nagagamit ko, na kumbaga nagiging guide mo pa din eh kumbaga elementary ka pa books na sya, outdated na." (Rather than looking at different books, I will ask AI. If you have doubts about the information, you will need to verify it through books to determine its accuracy. Back then, before I could teach, I needed to check all the information from textbooks. At times I even use the books I used when I was in elementary, but it is worrisome since textbooks published when I was still in elementary school may already be outdated.)

As the interviews continued, a similar pattern of observed behavior was seen in U1, U4, U5, U6, U7, U9, and U10, characterized by signs of relief, joy, and a calm, laid-back nature as they shared their thoughts on AI applications. In almost all participants' reactions, they were very straightforward about how they would describe AI and what it has done for their work. The narratives shared a common event where their hardships in producing valuable teaching materials were reduced by half, as Meta AI and Canva assisted them in creating functional materials that are produced with a prompt.

The workflow shift impacted the whole system. Their decision to integrate the application into their workflow was personal, enabling them to build upon existing materials and enhance them with the aid of an additional supportive tool.

These teachers have the capability and drive to ensure their students receive the best possible education. With AI applications now at their fingertips, they are even more empowered to do so.

From the behavior displayed, U4's face brightened as she shared how relieved she was about using AI applications, such as Meta AI and Canva. A laid-back demeanor was observed as she shared how the applications made her feel, explaining how they allowed her to finish her work early without compromising quality. She was grateful that, in her years of teaching, there would come a time when reports and presentations would be completed in a shorter amount of time, revealing valuable insights. U7 expressed evident appreciation for the AI applications, and the motion of his hands while narrating his experience demonstrated his confidence in using Meta AI and Canva. He first ensured that the lessons he designed aligned with what these applications offered, showing that before fully utilizing the tools, he checked for any discrepancies that could affect his decision to use them.

Skepticism with AI Communication

Theme 1: Accuracy and Authenticity

AI usage has come under public scrutiny, with debates centering on issues such as the accuracy and authenticity of its outputs. Accuracy is crucial, as it ensures that the information provided is correct and trustworthy. Teachers' acceptance or rejection of responses generated by Meta AI and Canva depends primarily on whether the information originates from credible sources and maintains a high standard of accuracy."

U5 reinforced that reliability is important to consider if you want to take the suggestion, *“Kasi nga kahit sa internet, sa internet o sa ibang mga site so minsan may mga information din tayo na mapapaisip tayo kung ito ba ay reliable or hindi. Nagkakaroon pa tayo ng comparison. Titingin tayo sa isang pinagkukunan ng information sa isa pang pinagkukunan ng information, parang kung alin dun yung mas pinakamadami na most the same ang sinasabi e di yun yung information na kukunin.”* (Even on the internet there is information where you will think twice if it is reliable or not, for that we go to other search engine then we can compare information, information that has the most similarities should be the one chosen.)

Being cautious is not wrong, especially for an educator who educates young minds in various subjects. Looking out and expecting the same amount of guidance should be given at the child's home. U5 has a more tactical approach in checking and validating the accuracy of the report given to her by the application.

For U5, trying to tweak the prompt used was something she used to evaluate the answer given by this AI application, *“Oo, kumbaga minsan hindi lang ako once nagtype nung information na gusto kong makita. Minsan medyo iniiba ko din, kasi tinitingnan ko din ano pa yung ibang information na ibibigay saken nung AI.”* (Yes, sometimes I retype the information I wanted to see. I change it a little to check what other information the AI could give.)

U5's way of vetting the information she received was to make minor alterations to her prompt to see what information she would obtain and whether it could provide better answers than the information she had received beforehand. This measure provided satisfaction to the user, as they had choices and sought information that aligned with their expectations.

At U6's end, seeking clarification assured that the information communicated with the application was aligned with the question:

“Meron din clarification na totoo ba yung sagot kasi parang nagdadoubt ako sa sagot na totoo ba ito, parang mali ata yung sagot neto sa tanong ko. Ang ginagawa ko pag may doubt pa-follow up, parang may doubt ka pa rin e di sa ibang apps ka na lang o kaya ay sa books, izearch mo na lang sa books para kung tama ba yung sagot din.” (There is clarification as well if the answer is correct. At times I doubt its correctness, so I make follow up questions. If I still have doubts, I use other apps or check on books whether the answer is right.)

In U6's mindset, it was not enough to accept the answer provided when prompted to apply. Evaluating the response is valuable because it filters out the answers that do not match one's needs. The case for U3 in terms of accuracy can be defined and equated with the level of satisfaction with the response received. Out of the 10 participants, she had used Meta AI the least due to dissatisfaction with the answers she received. She shared, *“Halimbawa dog climbing on the house or ladder, medyo iba kasi yung bigay saken na mga image compared dun sa magsearch ka na lang sa Google, mas maraming variation ka pang makukuha or mas marami pang uhm, ano ito picture na nabibigay saken instead na dun.”* (For example, I prompted Meta AI to generate an image of a dog climbing a ladder, but the suggestion given is not what I am really looking for, unlike when I use Google, where many variations can be seen, unlike using Meta AI.)

Explaining more of her experience, U3 shared: *“Sa AI may itatanong ka pero di sya specific na masasagot yung tanong mo. Tatanungin ka pa nya kung satisfied ka na ba dun o kung may panibago kang kelangan mo syang replayan ng halimbawa na specific mo dapat yung question mo. For example, yung sa “how to heal sprained*

ankle,” yung sagot nya saken, di sya ganun kadetailed, kelangan mo pa mag-ask ng another question para maging further or maging specified yung sagot sayo ni Meta.”

(Using AI, in my experience sometimes you will not get the answer you are looking for. It would ask if the answer provided is enough. For example, I have asked “how to heal a sprained ankle” but it did not give a complete explanation, I needed to make a follow-up to get further details.)

This interaction demonstrated that one can follow up to obtain more details if the initial prompt does not yield the expected results or if the user is dissatisfied with the answers received from these AI applications. It encourages getting familiar with crafting better prompts, knowing that topics and some complex requests for Meta AI, learning about this, and breaking down the request into manageable prompts.

Knowing the additional details of the query, crafting a better prompt with the necessary information would look like this: “Meta AI, please give a video of how to heal a sprained ankle.” This way, it could provide a more precise answer than “how to heal a sprained ankle” because specifications on what is being asked can result in a definite answer.

Being skeptical in usage is not a negative trait towards participating in using the application because, throughout the years, when teachers did not have applications like Meta AI and Canva, they effectively communicated and articulated their lessons to all their students with assurance that the information that came from books and publications was approved and correct. Now, with having public access to information over the internet and with applications that could assist in researching answers, it would be normal to feel a hint of doubt worrying if by prompting the application the teachers thought if the application understand what was asked,

wonder where the generated information came from, and from which sources was the knowledge shared taken.

Theme 2: Regulating AI Application Usage

U2 pointed out: “Syempre bata pa kasi yung learner namin eh, so kailangan nila ng gabay. Gabay ng magulang nila kay Meta AI, Canva naman bata ba sila eh hindi pa pwede. So ano guidance na lang sa paggamit...” (Our learners are still young; they need guidance. Guidance of parents for Meta AI usage and Canva, they are still young to use, so proper guidance is needed.)

Repeatedly advising on proper usage will help ensure that these applications are used for the intended purposes. In U8’s narration, she mentioned bad instances where AI applications have been used negatively:

U8 narrates, “...kagaya neto may hindi magandang incident ng sa page yung away, kaya lang di nagamit sa magandang paraan yung sa binasa mo yung respond kasi may specific topic silang di pinagkakaintindihan mapapansin mo sa sagot na generated lang, di gawa ng bata. Yun ang di maganda dun.” (...there was an incident concerning a student quarrel on an online group page. AI was used to provide an answer, but it was used for a negative purpose. There was a topic that they fought over; anyone can notice it was AI-generated and not written by a child, which is not good.)

Since then, she advised them to be cautious with their actions and to use applications like Meta AI responsibly, rather than using them to argue with their classmates. Creating restrictions and limitations on usage should be regulated.

In U3’s perspective upon usage, she shared, *“Yung di tayo magiging self-reliant tayo sa AI ganun. Ano, ano parin, di ko din masyadong sure, siguro maging*

mapanuri tayo maging analytic tayo sa nakukuha nating information kasi hindi valid kung yung information na binibigyan saten is yung ay tunay ano.” (We should not be reliant only on using AI. If you are still unsure, be observant and analyze the information received to validate the information given.)

U3 explained that the skill to determine if the information generated was right or wrong should be observed. Users should not fully accept information if it has not been validated. This highlights the negative aspects of AI usage. Suppose the person who will use it fully trusts the information without verifying its authenticity? In that case, it creates a destructive behavior of being heavily reliant and susceptible to misinformation.

In U10's mind, a comparison of traditional ways should still be observed, even with the existence of AI. She shared:

“In terms of sa work oo ang laking tulong ni AI pero in terms naman na pinag-aanuhan ng bata diba kinacater namin bata...kung yung mga bata ay aasa na lang kay AI wala na yung ano wala na yung study habit ng bata kasi ‘iclick ko na lang dito alam na yan ni Meta yung sagot’ so maisusulat man nila walang mareretain sa mind ng bata yun yung magiging disadvantage ng technology sa bata.” (In work, AI is beneficial, but for kids, if they rely entirely on AI, their study habits could disappear because everything is one click away from Meta AI generating an answer. Even if they wrote it down, they would not retain the information, and this would be a disadvantage of technology for the kids.)

Relying on AI applications like Meta AI has its advantages. However, it becomes a disadvantage if users become too reliant on usage, especially for kids still in the developmental stage of learning. Their cognitive skills and study habits should be developed to enhance their ability to learn more effectively in school. This

concern of U10 is valid, given that we are in the digital era, and AI applications are here to stay. Still, the adverse effects should not deter one from using the application for its advantages.

U10 continues, “Yan na yung papasok na yung part ng teacher tsaka yung magulang na lagi sila magkateam up, di pwedeng lagi si teacher lang kasi samin ilang oras lang si bata pagdating sa bahay. Pagdating sa bahay mas malaki yung oras ng magulang na dapat nasusubaybayan nila, so dapat magkakaran ng team-up si teacher atsaka si parent para bigyan ng limited time ng nasa bahay for gadget then tuturuan mo din sya kahit paano sa libro magbasa di puro AI. Kumbaga ituro kay bata na icompare si books tsaka si AI, ano yung magiging impact sa bata ganun din ang gagawin sa school. So, para hindi mawala yung study habit ng bata kailangan sa bahay at sa school may ginagawa sila.” (That's where the teacher and parent team-up, as the child only is with us a few hours unlike at home. Kids spend a lot more time at home so the parents should monitor the kids. They could give rules for limiting gadget usage and encourage them to read books. Let the kids compare books and AI, see the impact, and apply it at school, so that their study habits will not disappear.)

In support of knowing when to use applications, U10 recognized that these AI applications should be promoted as tools that assist, rather than replace, the human who thinks and ideates. Applications like these are created to help manage tasks so they are doable, but they should not entirely replace the person who works.

Skepticism comes in different forms; from the value teachers saw with the information received, the satisfaction the user felt to the generated response, or the skepticism of the result of voluntarily prompting AI applications with daily usage that may result with a change mindset stemmed on the users end that leads to over

relying on the application with doing task, giving them autonomy over the user with decision-making.

The act of relying on or not communicating with AI applications highlights how they perceive AI applications and the trust they have in communicating with them. Their actions, such as considering the generated responses, making follow-ups, or their choice not to utilize the applications' suggestions, stem from their belief and decision about what AI is. Weighing on their mind the reasons why they would communicate with these applications, how they will communicate, and when they will use them. Having an overall criterion with how they view AI, and how much the reason validates their actions and mindset when utilizing the application.

AI's Perceived Identity (Who is AI?)

Theme 1: AI's Different Roles

Following the last theme discussed is skepticism regarding the use of AI applications. However, drawing a clearer picture of how teachers identify AI applications raises a question: Is it just a tool? Alternatively, somewhere between communication and interaction, the bond has been formed, creating a persona for the AI application itself.

U9 shared: *“Ano lang din, hindi ako fully syempre ano kasi nga yung natanong ko ay gamot e di syempre nakalagay dun sabi ni Meta AI para mas sure ka kailangan mo mag ano sa doctor. Ayun nakalagay naman dun, parang meron silang mga reminder. Parang may ano sila.”* (For me I don't fully accept, because my question is about medication and as indicated by Meta AI as a disclaimer for assurance I need to check with a doctor.)

This suggests that AI application users either accept or decline the information based on their knowledge and trust in the information shared. Whether to trust AI for medical inquiries ultimately depends on the user's judgment and discretion.

From her narrative as well U9 continued sharing her experience with AI, *“Kukuha lang akong idea, kaya pag ano sasabihin saken ni Doc nung first na bagong bago pa lang akong mommy parang mga 4 months 6 months e di nagtanong ako kay Doc sabi ko “Doc bawal po bang uminom ng uminom pa ng water yung baby? Milk pa lang?” Sabi nya saan mo nalaman yun Ginoogle mo yan no sabi nung pedia ng baby ko. Kasi parang ano nga sinearch ko, pwede na bang uminom ng gantong months na baby.”* (I want to get an idea, I was a first-time mom around 4 to 6 months when I asked, “Doc, can the baby drink water? Or Milk only?” Then the Doctor commented on where I got the information and whether it was available on Google. It is because at the time I did the research about whether the baby could already drink water within these months.)

This ensures that individuals have a choice about what to do with the information obtained, including checking other information and resources where they would acquire what they want to know.

U9's decision to ask a professional to answer her query regarding her baby is a clear sign that, in her case, getting the answers from the expert (doctor) is what she needs. This suggests that accepting or rejecting an AI's response is directly influenced by the risk it entails.

Applications like Meta AI and Canva are not limited to using them for schoolwork, as they offer a range of additional features and options for their use. The *learning experience is not limited to academic purposes but also extends to real-life*

situations that enhance one's problem-solving capabilities. In U9's experience, she shared a past concern with a student and has used the application for advice:

"Ito yung estudyante ko may gamot yung baby ko na natira tapos meron sugat yung estudyante ko, sinearch ko pwede ba yung gamot na yun sa gantong ano, gantong skin ano nya allergy nya. Kasi yung anak ko nagka-allergy tapos sinearch ko kung pwede kasi wala daw syang gamot eh, yun tiningnan ko kung pwede. Maibibigay naman nila yung detail ano eh." (My baby has excess allergy medication. I have searched to see if the medicine can be used for a particular allergy, in case it could be used by my student for their wound. Details are given when searched in Meta AI.)

This mindset fostered the idea that AI applications are not limited to acting as tools to assist with school-based knowledge and teaching; they also extend beyond improving analytical and rational thinking in decision-making.

From U4's end, she brought up her relationship and how these applications have helped her better understand it. *"Oo nagagamit ko sya, halimbawa, yung sa anak ko, minsan nag-away kami ng anak ko. 'Di naman nag-away, kumbaga di ko lang sya naintindihan. "How to deal with teenagers?" Ganyan kasi teenager na yung anak ko."* (I have used it, for example, when my child and I have a misunderstanding. I search "how to deal with teenagers" as my child is already in their teen years.)

This opened an avenue that, along with the personal improvements made by using the applications for personal gain, demonstrated that users acquired the skill of being proactive in helping, learning, and improving their communication style, as they gained insight into how to be better. The integration of these applications enhanced their teaching capability, broadening their teaching skills and making them better citizens.

By attributing an identity to the application, teachers formed a perceived bond with it. In their communication with AI, they often regarded it as a co-collaborator in instructional tasks. However, this perception shifted when seeking information on sensitive topics such as medicine or parenting, where the AI assumed varying roles — expert, advisor, or mentor. This dynamic illustrates how teachers moved beyond viewing AI as a mere tool, instead recognizing it as a quasi-entity whose responses they valued and respected. Such perceptions influence how teachers continue to engage with AI to verify information, seek guidance, or co-construct ideas, indicating an evolving relationship that extends beyond functional use.”

This suggests that, in addition to having their agenda for utilizing an application, continued usage is supported by reason. The ongoing conversation is rooted in convenience, comfort, familiarity, and personal connection. The idea of usage, accepting or rejecting the responses comes with the mindset shift of what the teachers see AI as, in the narratives shared where AI has been given the identity of being an assistant, friend, doctor or adviser is the teachers personal point of view of who AI is for them and how they would treat the application, and by acknowledging that persona or identity how does it affect their subject to reason of accepting the response, using the application, and reliance with the application.

Ontological Insights of Teacher-AI Communication

The narratives unveiled lived experiences to understand the teachers' motives in utilizing Meta AI and Canva applications. They revealed how these applications have improved the course of their teaching careers. Nine out of 10 participants agreed that these applications have expedited their tasks.

This human-machine interaction brought a new reality in terms of how to view AI, not only viewing it as a tool that responds to assist, but as an entity that can influence, redefine, and reshape communication in general, as AI is not a mere instrument that creates meaning, but it lives and exists in a developing reality.

Recognizing AI as having a distinct perceived identity redefines its significance for teachers. Its function ultimately depends on how it is positioned within their practice: is AI simply a tool, or does it serve as a collaborator or advisor? For users, this raises critical questions about the role AI occupies in their professional and personal decision-making.

Accepting its existence and recognizing that AI can go beyond being a tool involves how they treat and communicate with the application. Restrictions on communicating with AI do not diminish the value people see in AI, but learning that AI is limited in what it can do. The process provides clarity on what they can request from the application.

The narratives from U4, U7, and U9 are examples of seeing AI applications as more than just tools, communicating with personal dilemmas, seeing AI applications as a mentor, or asking for quick medical advice, showing that their actions toward asking the application personal questions equate with the trust they have in utilizing the application. AI's ability to influence and shape humans is primarily determined by the individual's willingness to allow AI to have an impact on them. AI applications in the current reality are not perceived as an additional thing that lives alongside people; they are an integral part of people's lives.

Living among people is acknowledging that AI applications are everywhere, and there are a few in plain sight that are open to the public, such as Meta AI and

Canva. Having the capability and knowledge to communicate with them effectively is a leverage in living in the Digital Era.

AI in Developing Reality: Behavioral Change

AI has emerged as a transformative force, offering a range of applications that bring futuristic concepts to essential parts of people's daily lives. Restructuring the academic landscape, AI has given opportunities for personalization, efficiency, and improved academic outcomes (University of San Diego, 2024)

User-friendly features promote efficiency as the applications are convenient, and automated task assistance reduces workload. Juggling the construction of instructional materials alongside crafting daily lessons, AI supported the teacher in managing tasks for improved classroom management.

Teachers utilized AI applications to enhance the quality of instructional materials, create presentations efficiently, and facilitate more enjoyable and engaging classroom discussions. AI should be viewed as a tool, but in reality, humans and AI are not functioning as distinct entities; instead, they act as collaborators in creating ideas.

However, did the improved quality of teaching and learning result from the use of AI?

In relation to the participants' narratives, their initiative to utilize the AI applications resulted in tangible and digital outcomes of their planned ideas. AI applications may give out suggestions and information. Still, when using, accepting, or adapting the information generated, the teacher should consider what will be helpful and appropriate in their class. Having an application that a teacher can rely on to expedite results and assist with tasks that require much time has been a great relief,

making the workload more manageable. The improved quality of teaching is an incidental result of the improved quality of life overall for the teacher.

Nine out of 10 mentioned how the tools have made their lives easier, and they felt relieved knowing that this application gave an extra helping hand for their work. AI is transforming users into different thinkers, and teachers and AI have become co-creators and collaborators, shifting from being knowledge providers to co-creating knowledge alongside AI.

Familiarity with AI and its capabilities prompts the user to think differently, depending on the information requested. For example, when a teacher prompts the application for information in a science subject, the generated response is validated by the teacher to determine what is needed. The effort to filter and accept the information originated from the teacher's initiative to trust the information provided by the AI application.

The teacher's choice to accept or reject the information stemmed from their ability to trust AI as co-collaborators, and filtering the information before using it for reports and lessons acknowledged that AI applications, such as Meta AI and Canva, have their strengths and weaknesses. By knowing this, they can validate the information given before sharing it with the class.

These technologies should be viewed as tools, but in an ontological sense, they are more than just digital tools, as they have become integral to shaping how teachers perform their work. The new reality of teaching and learning is beginning to shift as data gathering in lesson creation differs from what it was before. From gathering information from books or other publications and verifying its authenticity as a reference material to obtaining information online, students are developing the critical thinking skill of checking the validity of knowledge.

The narratives of U5, U6, and U9 emphasized this mindset. Sharing how different their lives are now compared to before the applications, because, along with the fast way of gathering information, the internet is filled with varying types of information coming from various sources and authors. Authentic information is essential to confirm that it originated from a legitimate source.

The new reality is that AI communication has changed teachers' perspectives on data gathering and filtering. This changed behavior resulted from adapting to machine communication (AI prompting) to get considerable and significant information to use in teaching. Adapting to what the teacher thinks the application knows, AI generates information it believes the teacher needs, creating a personalized bond that results in better understanding in future interactions.

Choosing the right keywords yields reliable results, ultimately leading to better and more valuable outcomes. Familiarity with each other's intellect helps in learning how to prompt better, tailoring it to the user's point of view (Siegel, 2023).

Prompting is a process of considering who your audience is, to fit the information needed. Once generated, it is the teacher's initiative to ask for follow-up or clarify any information that has been generated, and the same applies to knowing when to accept or reject a response. Learning what is usable, needed, and authentic is part of the user's responsibility to filter out the information.

In terms of regulating usage, these applications will stay. AI is no longer a stranger; in the educational landscape, it has become a co-creator of information, working in partnership with teachers to enhance learning. This ontological reality is that users are not simply adapting to new technology; they are inhabiting a new identity. AI will continue to evolve as users do, and as the educational system does, it will also be shaped by intelligent systems. The ongoing changes and opportunities

now lie in how teachers and users choose their realities in developing the world with AI.

Holding great power comes with awareness, as AI did not ask the teachers to change, but it required them to. The choice to learn how AI applications communicate more effectively is knowledge gained through the process of trying to communicate. Their change in behavior cannot be attributed solely to the influence of AI; rather, it is an active action made by the user.

The improved quality of life can be compared to having a lighter workload, longer hours for thought, and less manual labor in executing and creating instructional materials, as they have AI to rely on, making the process less cumbersome. However, even with AI applications existing it will not simply do their task without the prompts provided, the added advantage of using the application is the freedom of not exhausting additional hours with checking resources over at the library to use for reports or buying colored papers to use for designing visual aids are the least worry on the teacher's mind. By doing so, they have enough energy to teach and enough emotional bandwidth to connect and engage with their students more effectively.

Becoming and Resisting: Tension with Human-AI Partnership

Apart from using AI and accepting the application, there are contradicting views on how it should be used. Some of the teachers have shared their valid concerns, and in doing so, it has affected how they use the application. U8's narrative highlighted the troubling situation one of her students encountered, which affected how AI should be used. Continuous guidance and advice should be adhered to.

Partnership with AI as co-creators or other identifying personas brings tension to the relationship. Simultaneously trusting and distrusting using the AI application, putting restrictions on when to use it, and for what reason. This is similar to the narrative shared by U5 and her mindset when utilizing the application. The simultaneous trust and distrust behavior towards the application is a result of knowing what the AI application is capable of. The lack of trust or change in behavior due to double-checking the information shared by the application is an effect of knowing that the application can make mistakes, depending on how it understands the prompt given.

Consideration of when AI should be relied on should be discussed. It is a given that users are not entirely independent, and with AI, they should not be. Still, there would be situations where human autonomy should be asserted, not letting the application decide what is right and what should be done. Living in the new reality with AI requires conscious and ethical actions, rather than unquestioningly adopting it. Humans are asked to work responsibly with AI when merging humans and machines.

Communicating with AI applications requires caution, as these applications are still prone to errors when interacting with machines. Shared information should be accompanied by valuing the correctness of the information being learned, to learn how to prompt the application better, make follow-ups, and internalize when the user should utilize the application.

Chapter 5

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

Communication is an ongoing process of creating and disseminating information, adapting to new emerging technologies and realities. The question “How do public school teachers communicate with digital tools like Meta AI and Canva, and how do these applications shape their instructional practices?” has been explored and answered using Narrative Inquiry, which views the shared stories from an Ontological perspective, discussing the new reality of human-machine interaction.

This study analyzed and restoryed the lived experiences of 10 public school teachers regarding their use of Meta AI and Canva in their work. AI applications are not solely designed for the education sector; they are created to assist users with their tasks. These applications can benefit various fields, and education is, fortunately, one of the fields for which they are specifically designed.

From traditionally adapting teaching methods, teachers have transitioned to accepting and utilizing digital tools to support them. This interaction has led to the new reality they now live in.

Using restorying and analysis in the ontological vision, narratives were gathered and interpreted into four interrelated topics: Communicating with Meta AI and Canva, Workflow Shift (Meta AI and Canva Usage), Skepticism with AI Communication, and AI’s Perceived Identity (Who is AI?).

The first topic addressed the themes of crafting the prompt, consideration, and relatability. Bringing to light what happened within the Human-AI communication process, and within that process, what are the key considerations for creating a good

prompt for Meta AI and Canva? Prompting the applications effectively by giving clear, non-complex commands will deliver satisfactory results, as the application can gain a better understanding of what the user is asking for.

The workflow shift showed the transition and merged methods for teaching as traditional begin to shift to digital like AI application usage, due to this transition in the process of validating the information shared by the application is the process of checking the accuracy and authenticity of the information knowing the boundaries in using the application, discerning that regulating the application is a must to avoid conflict. The boundary of usage comes with a concern of being aware when to use the applications and for how long; overdependence should not be the result of learning how to utilize these applications. Accepting or rejecting a response entails determining what is required, what is acceptable, and whether it is authentic.

Acknowledging the changes that have helped expedite the teachers' tasks, leading to a more manageable workload, which equates to a better, more manageable, and improved quality of life.

Skepticism about AI Communication brought diverse insights into AI application utilization, as its existence did not guarantee that anyone who had learned to use the application would continue to use it. From the narratives gathered, it is evident that some individuals are not keen on using the application and share their doubts about utilizing it in their work.

Continuing the discussion is the topic of AI's perceived Identity, as the process of communication with AI is rooted in how teachers perceive it. Continued communication revealed that teachers did not view AI as merely a tool; instead, they perceived it in the role they had associated with it. This leads to a discussion under Ontology, where the data reveals insights into how, in the reality of where AI lives

among us, it acknowledges its entity, and the continued usage stems from the trust given by users who use the application. Within this relationship comes a realization that the utilization of AI has led to changed behavior among users as they adapt to communicating with AI. The old method of teaching and learning is slowly being left behind, as the new process of obtaining information takes hold. This change has brought tension regarding how people use AI applications, as they continue to experience both trust and distrust in the application. The boundary of usage raises concerns about being aware of when to use the applications and for how long; overdependence should not be the result of learning how to utilize these applications. In communicating with machines, response comes with requirements for what is needed, what is acceptable, and if it is authentic.

Conclusions

Four interrelated topics emerge to answer, “how do public school teachers communicate with digital tools like Meta AI and Canva and how do these applications shape their instructional practices” (1) Communicating with Meta AI and Canva, (2) Workflow Shift (Meta AI and Canva Usage), (3) Skepticism with AI Communication, and (4) AI’s Perceived Identity (Who is AI?). By narrative inquiry, diverse perspectives have been accumulated.

The study highlighted the teachers’ relationship with AI applications Meta AI and Canva, in the context of modern education/teaching. As the teachers narrate their experiences using the application, it is revealed that, aside from using it for work, they also utilize it for personal purposes.

Choosing the application is a matter of convenience, as the user-friendly features of the application persuaded them to utilize it. Instant results are eye-catching to

anyone who wants to complete their work quickly. The teachers have their basis on how they prompt these applications.

The study concludes that when communicating with these AI applications, behavior change often accompanies it as a result of the choice, as communication with a machine differs from communicating with humans. The limitation on how to communicate makes it vulnerable to giving information that users might not need. Complex queries should be broken into parts, and clear and concise prompts are highly advised.

AI applications may encounter difficulty in understanding queries if they are created with complex language; being direct and to the point, with clear and concise commands, would allow the application to generate better results.

Effective communication with AI requires an evolving skill set. Teachers craft their prompts with intention; they do not accept what is generated but rather question and validate the information. They aligned it with their objectives and took into consideration who the listeners are and what information would be most beneficial for them. Reflecting an understanding that with AI utilization, it is not enough for the user to prompt the application merely; the user should guide the interaction, not the other way around.

Even if AI is a powerful application, its way of knowing information and learned behavior is up to the users who prompt it. AI applications are a product of the human mind, meaning they can only possess knowledge that the human mind possesses. Therefore, humans should have autonomy over the application.

The practice of evaluating the generated responses reflects the users' awareness of fact-checking. In a professional setting, they are curators of knowledge, not just consumers of what technology tries to feed them. Using

discretion and engaging selectively and mindfully with the application emphasizes that AI is a responsive system that reflects human input.

Utilization of these applications is a choice, the education landscape has been progressing, and along with the continued changes are the growing demands with the teachers' tasks, with AI applications available to use, people saw the opportunity that this application can be utilized in the education sector as it offers assistance, acting as a support with the teachers with completing their tasks.

Teachers engage with these tools as collaborators, integrating them into their planning and adapting to their new reality as AI assists in creating lessons for a diverse set of learners.

As teachers view AI as more than just a tool, out of the 10 participants, AI played different roles that have shaped and influenced them, impacting how they educate their students and balance their work with their personal lives. The decision to change behavior when interacting with AI applications is a personal choice, but it largely depends on the reason for the change. The change in behavior is linked with better communication and usage of AI applications, seeing and adapting to the level of comprehension they see AI has.

AI is not only a tool, but it is also acknowledged as having its functional entity. However, it still needs guidance and understanding; complete reliance on it is not advised, as there will be situations that still require human autonomy, as these AI applications have their limitations.

AI has its entity; it lives among us, but along with knowing its strengths, it acknowledges that AI applications are limited as well; it has their weaknesses. Knowing that when the prompt is too complicated the application might encounter difficulty in answering the query of the teacher, or validating an information since

they rely with online information fed to them over the internet, they would only answer with the available resource they could look for, so if the result generated is incorrect the choices the user have is to recreate the prompt, make a follow up, and have clearer more precise prompt.

Therefore, in response to the research question of how public teachers communicate with Meta AI and Canva, it is through intentional, purposeful, and strategic usage. Acting as both users and regulators, their interaction is characterized by a reflective acceptance of responses and an awareness of how to interact effectively with the application while upholding the standards they have in their work. The shaping of instructional practice does not come from the tool itself; rather, it is in the teacher's initiative to manage, evaluate, adapt, and integrate its use.

Recommendation

The following points are recommended based on the findings of this study:

1. The study revealed how teachers manage to communicate and utilize AI applications. For further studies, understanding how students view AI and how they respond to AI-supported content taught would provide a valuable perspective.
2. Further studies are needed to understand how reliance on AI applications might magnify or limit teachers' autonomy.
3. Investigate whether a user's upbringing should be considered in relation to their adoption of AI utilization.
4. Explore the school policies and practices that reveal the barriers and deliberate solutions for effectively regulating AI usage, promoting AI's strengths without undermining the system by advancing technology.

5. Analyze whether the utilization of AI applications affects how teachers collaborate with colleagues in constructing instructional materials.

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APPENDIX A

Table 2: *Open Coding and Axial Coding*

Open and Axial coding were used to compare, identify patterns, and group the 35 excerpts with similarities. Four main themes emerged, each with its subthemes.

The first theme, **Communicating with Meta AI and Canva**, has two subthemes: (1) Prompt Crafting Process and (2) Consideration and Relatability. The first subtheme established is about the communication process of interacting with AI applications. *AI Communication, Things to Consider When Talking to AI Apps, and Communicating with AI Applications* are the topics covered. The narratives share similar perspectives on their experiences interacting with AI. However, in a more profound sense, they were sharing the communication process they have established when interacting with AI applications. The second subtheme came from the excerpts expressing how the teachers give importance with knowing who their listeners are, codes: *Factors in AI message, Consideration, Consideration to listeners, and Adapting to audience*, shares a pattern of understanding the point of view of the narrator that gives importance with the involvement of the audience before they act or prompt the application.

The next theme is **Workflow Shift (Meta AI and Canva Usage)** with two subthemes: (1) Instantly Generated Results and (2) Traditional or Digital (Merge of Methods). The first subtheme was determined by the shared narratives that explain speed (rate of movement). The selected codes are: *Fast result, Task expedited, Less stress for work needs, One click, Easy access, Convenient access, and Learning fast with AI*. This explains how speed in different contexts relates to AI usage, and as a result, the subtheme *Instant Generated Results* has been created. Under the same theme, a subtheme titled “*Traditional to Digital (Merge of Methods)*”

was developed, and four codes were identified: *Old method*, *Comparison of new and old methods*, *AI included in teaching*, and *New method*. The interpretation of this category relates to narratives shared experiences that discuss transitions related to teaching, and their perspective on utilizing AI applications while remembering how different it was back then.

Third topic, **Skepticism with AI Communication**, with the subthemes (1) Accuracy and Authenticity, and (2) Regulating AI Application Usage. Narratives from U5, U6, and U3 reveal similar patterns of doubting, questioning, and verifying the information generated by the applications. *Checking for authenticity*, *Legitimacy*, *Correctness*, *usefulness*, and *Helpfulness of data* are the codes labeled from the teachers' narratives. At the same time, the subtheme of *Regulating AI Application Usage* narratives from U2, U8, U3, and U10 expressed their different concerns and opinions on AI utilization. This section provides guidance and awareness on using the application. Codes, *AI application guidance*, *unfortunate events related to AI usage*, *regulating AI*, and *determining when to use AI* have been grouped under the third theme.

Lastly, the subtheme from **AI's Perceived Identity (Who is AI?)**, "AI's Different Roles." This last theme brings light to narratives with codes relating to perceived persona. Codes, *AI identity*, *Professional Identity*, *AI as a call a friend*, and *AI as a personal advisor* demonstrate AI playing different roles from the teachers' perspective.

The codes and created themes serve a purpose in interpreting data that have helped determine and answer the question, "How do public school teachers communicate with digital tools like Meta AI and Canva, and how do these applications shape their instructional practices?"

User	Open Code	Axial Code	Theme	Excerpt
U2	AI Communication	Prompt Crafting Process	Communicating with Meta AI and Canva	<p><i>“Straight forward na pagtatanong, yung kung anong gusto mong malaman. Kumbaga straight to the point po na, kunwari ang hinahanap nyo po ay ilan ang letters sa alphabet. ‘Di na paligoy ligoy pa. Kasi syempre pag ano pa tayo kung saan pupunta pa...”</i></p>
U1	Things to consider talking to AI apps	Prompt Crafting Process	Communicating with Meta AI and Canva	<p><i>“Halimbawa tungkol sa “living things” dapat yun isearch mo, parang ano yung theme, parang ganun. Kasi pag wala kang theme na isearch ang dami pong lumalabas, dami mong options, ang dami mong iscroll, eh kung nagsearch ka ng halimbawa about Math, halimbawa background about “Mathematics for kids” so lalabas na sya dun, kasi pag hindi specific ang dami mong pamimilian dun, pag nagsearch ka po lalabas na yung mga option about dun o yung tema, theme about sa kailangan mo.”</i></p>
U9	Things to consider talking to AI apps	Prompt Crafting Process	Communicating with Meta AI and Canva	<p><i>“...halimbawa may gusto akong, kunyari gusto kong mag gawa ng certificate,</i></p>

search ko lang dun kunwari pang sports certificate yung ano yung pang honors namin sa mga bata yung mga pang achiever mga ganan. Isearch mo lang yun magbibigay na sila ng mga ano eh, ng mga set na pamimilian mo. Maganda sya.”

U2	Communicating with Ai	Prompt Crafting Process	Communicating with Meta AI and Canva	<i>“Binabasa ko sya tapos pinipili ko lang kung alin yung pwede, yung importante, yung pwede kong ilagay sa narrative ko. ‘Di ko sya pwedeng, ano baka tayo maplagiarism pag kinuha ko ng buo yun, kumbaga pinipili ko lang kung alin ang gusto kong kuhanin. Yun yung pag-evaluate ko sa binibigay na sagot ng Meta AI or ng Canva.”</i>
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U1	Factors in AI message	Consideration and Relatability	Communicating with Meta AI and Canva	<i>“Ngayon ang bilis, pero syempre naman, yung nakuha mo sa AI ay lahat yun applicable sa, halimbawa magtuturo ka sa bata, syempre iseselect mo, icheck mo din alin yung mas mapapadali, mas mababaw. Kasi syempre usually baka napakalalim na nung mga terminologies mga ano,</i>
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medyo dapat aanuhin mo. Dapat abot kaya nung mga aanuhan mo.”

U6	Consideration	Consideration and Relatability	Communicating with Meta AI and Canva	<i>“Pag mas madali kasi tatanggapin ko, kasi mas madali na yung application nya eh, pagka mahirap kasi pag ang daming mga pag madami ka pang ilalagay sa application sa program na sinuggest nya, di ko gagawin yun, dun na ako sa may madali, kesa dun sa mahirap. Kumbaga ano madami siyang design, pipili ako ng simpleng design na madali kong mababago, kesa dun sa design na madami kang aayusin.”</i>
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U2	Consideration to listeners	Consideration and Relatability	Communicating with Meta AI and Canva	<i>“Yung pinakang simpleng paraan na maiintindihan ng bata yung kukunin namin, yung pag kinuha namin mas mapapadali maintindihan ng mga bata. Dahil ang hawak nyo po ay kinder.”</i>
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U2	Adapting to audience	Consideration and Relatability	Communicating with Meta AI and Canva	<i>“Ito yun, nilayout ko lang sya sa Canva, ito yung five senses...layout mo lang yan tapos ikaw na ang bahala maggawa. Madami na akong nagawa</i>
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pero ito yung pinakang-nagamit ko sa pagtuturo ko.”

U1	Fast Results	Instant Generated Results	Workflow Shift (Meta AI and Canva Usage)	<i>“I use Meta AI and Canva for ano rin po para sa mas mabilis na makakuha ng information, so aside from Google mas mabilis rin po kasi makakuha ng mga information sa Meta AI mabilis yung information na maaari mong makuha, sa Canva naman po ginagamit po namin ito sa mga, mga layouts, tulad ng mga poster.”</i>
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U4	Tasks expedited	Instant Generated Results	Workflow Shift (Meta AI and Canva Usage)	<i>“Dati yung ginagawa ko ng ilang oras, siguro mga two hours, three hours. Ngayon kayang kaya mong gawin, ngayon mga wala pang 1 minute, isang click lang, siguro mga one-minute pag clinick mo pero ano ayan na. Diretso na.”</i>
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U4	Less stress for work needs	Instant Generated Results	Workflow Shift (Meta AI and Canva Usage)	<i>“... ‘Di na ako nahihirapan, Isang click mo lamang nadito na yung letter o kaya, make me a lesson plan. Papagawa din ako sa kanya ng lesson plan na tungkol sa adverb o kaya about verb. O sa math,</i>
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pagbukas mo noon kumpleto na, hindi na ako mag-iisip madali na lang pala netong AI na ito. Parang pinadali yung buhay ko.”

U5	One click	Instant Generated Results	Workflow Shift (Meta AI and Canva Usage)	<i>“Kasi ang dali ang bilis, kumbaga isang type mo lang pag meron kang gustong makuhang info, makukuha mo. Kahit nga yung sample Daily Lesson Log (DLL) or lesson plan ng teacher eh may lumalabas na information. Sample yung co-teacher ko sa math kasi may time na kumbaga ay lack of ah sabihin na nating nagkulang kami ng activities sa bata kumbaga nakapagbigay na kami ng drill 1, drill 2, or activity 1 and activity 2, na kinulang kami so halimbawa ganun makakapag-add ka ng gawain or pwede pang activities sa kanila with the use of AI.”</i>
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U6	Easy access	Instant Generated Results	Workflow Shift (Meta AI and Canva Usage)	<i>“Madaling maaccess yung dalawa, yung Meta AI, pag may mga questions asked ka, madaling sumagot. Yung Canva naman magagamit mo sya pag gagawa ng powerpoint</i>
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presentation, sa akin ah ginagamit ko sya sa powerpoint presentation. Mga paggagawa lang na yun nga, program, yun ganun lang.”

U7	Convenient Access	Instant Generated Results	Workflow Shift (Meta AI and Canva Usage)	<i>“Ginagamit namin sa teachers’ guide kumbaga ano naman sya kumbaga wala naman syang discrepancy, kumbaga parehas din naman sya mas kumbaga ano advance lang yung knowledge na makukuha kay Meta AI.”</i>
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U7	Convenient Access	Instant Generated Results	Workflow Shift (Meta AI and Canva Usage)	<i>“Pwede ng gumawa ng videos sa Canva may mga ready-made na silang mga template dun gagamitin mo na lang kumbaga ah tawag dito lagay ka na lang ng lagay ng mga pictures tapos iaayos mo na lang then ikaw na yung bahalang mag animations, ganun kaya kumbaga yung tools na yan hanggang ngayon now ginagamit ko pa din sa pagtuturo. Wala ako ditong maiaano sayo eh yung kahit sa mga school yung ID ng bata yun sa Canva din namin.”</i>
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U7	Learning fast with AI	Instant Generated Results	Workflow Shift (Meta AI and Canva Usage)	<i>“Meta AI kasi when it comes to lesson na kailangan mong magresearch kumbaga para magkaroon ka din ng review or deep understanding dun sa lesson na gusto mong ituro sa bata para mas lalo silang nakainteract malaking tulong din, maganda oo.”</i>
U9	Old method	Traditional to Digital (Merge of Methods)	Workflow Shift (Meta AI and Canva Usage)	<i>“Sobrang laki syempre kasi ngayon ano ka na lang type ka na lang ng idea mo type mo lang diba. Kunwari sa encyclopedia hahanapin mo pa yung letter diba meron tayong set ng encyclopedia hahanapin mo pa yung letter kung ano yung naiisip mong hanapin diba ganun po. Kaya saken sobrang laki ng impact ng technology kumbaga sa atin yung mga ganyan, syempre mas napadali.”</i>
U10	Comparison of new and old method	Traditional to Digital (Merge of Methods)	Workflow Shift (Meta AI and Canva Usage)	<i>“Nung time na nung time na ano pa lang, wala pa yung mga ganyang technology talagang mahirap kasi lahat gagawin mo pasulat. Gagawa ka ng ano isusulat mo, visual aids, kailangan mo mag gupit o magdrawing then nung</i>

dumating itong mga technology natin kay Canva madali na magpresent ng picture. Mapagsasama sama mo sya sa isang page lang.... ngayon na dumating din itong si AI Meta kumbaga yung mga behind question na hindi mo agad masasagot na kailangan mong magresearch iclick mo lang kay AI ayon na may result ka kaagad. Yun yung kagandahan ng technology natin ngayon kay Canva tsaka sa ayon.”

U8	AI included in teaching	Traditional to Digital (Merge of Methods)	Workflow Shift (Meta AI and Canva Usage)	<i>“...mas madali na kasi mas less na yung ano, yung time na gugugulin mo paggawa ng slide, kagaya nga nung sinasabi ko na, dati pipili ka ng magandang background, font size, o kaya yung image na iinsert. Nandoon sa Canva, talagang mas eksakto mo halimbawa yung sa Science, Values, yung may specific topic. “</i>
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U6	New method	Traditional to Digital (Merge of Methods)	Workflow Shift (Meta AI and Canva Usage)	<i>...kasi ano kesa hanap ka sa books, sa iba-iba pang books edi dun ka na lang magtanong sa AI, tapos pag may doubt ka tsaka ka na lang</i>
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magtitingin dun sa books, kung mali ba o tama yun. 'Di katulad dati na pag magtuturo ka ang dami mong reference book na tinitingnan. Tapos pag ano iba-iba pa yung information na nadun kasi nga mga ano di updated, may times na mga books ko ng elementary nagagamit ko, na kumbaga nagiging guide mo pa din eh kumbaga elementary ka pa books na sya, outdated na. “

U5	Checking for authenticity	Accuracy and Authenticity	Skepticism with AI Communication	<i>“Kasi nga kahit sa internet, sa internet o sa ibang mga site so minsan may mga information din tayo na mapapaisip tayo kung ito ba ay reliable or hindi. Nagkakaroon pa tayo ng comparison. Titingin tayo sa isang pinagkukunan ng information sa isa pang pinagkukunan ng information, parang kung alin dun yung mas pinakamadami na most the same ang sinasabi edi yun yung information na kukunin.”</i>
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U5	Legitimacy	Accuracy and Authenticity	Skepticism with AI Communication	<i>“Oo, kumbaga minsan hindi lang ako once nagtype nung information na gusto kong makita. Minsan medyo iniiba</i>
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ko din, kasi tinitingnan ko din ano pa yung ibang information na ibibigay saken nung AI.”

U6	Correctness	Accuracy and Authenticity	Skepticism with AI Communication	<i>“Meron din clarification na totoo ba yung sagot kasi parang nagdodoubt ako sa sagot na totoo ba ito, parang mali ata yung sagot neto sa tanong ko. Ang ginagawa ko pag may doubt pa-follow up, parang may doubt ka pa rin edi sa ibang apps ka na lang o kaya ay sa books, ısearch mo na lang sa books para kung tama ba yung sagot din.”</i>
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U3	Usefulness and correctness	Accuracy and Authenticity	Skepticism with AI Communication	<i>“Halimbawa dog climbing on the house or ladder, medyo iba kasi yung bigay saken na mga image compare dun sa magsearch ka na lang sa Google, mas maraming variation ka pang makukuha or mas marami pang uhm, ano ito picture na nabibigay saken instead na dun.”</i>
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U3	Helpfulness of data	Accuracy and Authenticity	Skepticism with AI Communication	<i>“Sa AI may itatanong ka pero di sya specific na masasagot yung tanong mo. Tatanungin ka pa nya kung satisfied ka</i>
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na ba dun o kung may panibago kang kelangan mo syang replayan ng halimbawa na specific mo dapat yung question mo. For example, yung sa “how to heal sprained ankle,” yung sagot nya saken, di sya ganun kadetailed, kelangan mo pa mag-ask ng another question para maging farther or maging specified yung sagot sayo ni Meta.”

U2	AI application Guidance	Regulating AI application Usage	Skepticism with AI Communication	<i>“Syempre bata pa kasi yung learner namin eh, so kailangan nila ng gabay. Gabay ng magulang nila kay Meta AI, Canva naman bata ba sila eh hindi pa pwede. So ano guidance na lang sa paggamit...”</i>
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U8	Unfortunate Event with AI Usage	Regulating AI application Usage	Skepticism with AI Communication	<i>“...kagaya neto may hindi magandang incident ng sa page yung away, kaya lang di nagamit sa magandang paraan yung sa binasa mo yung respond kasi may specific topic silang di pinagkakaintindihan mapapansin mo sa sagot na generated lang, di gawa ng bata. Yun ang di maganda dun.”</i>
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U3	Regulating AI	Regulating AI application Usage	Skepticism with AI Communication	<p><i>“Yung di tayo magiging self-reliant tayo sa AI ganun. Ano, ano parin, di ko din masyadong sure, siguro maging mapanuri tayo maging analytic tayo sa nakukuha nating information kasi hindi valid kung yung information na binibigyan saten is yung ay tunay ano.”</i></p>
U10	When to use AI	Regulating AI application Usage	Skepticism with AI Communication	<p><i>“In terms of sa work oo ang laking tulong ni AI pero in terms naman na pinag-aanuhan ng bata diba kinacater namin bata...kung yung mga bata ay aasa na lang kay AI wala na yung ano wala na yung study habit ng bata kasi ‘iclick ko na lang dito alam na yan ni Meta yung sagot’ so maisusulat man nila walang marerretain sa mind ng bata yun yung magiging disadvantage ng technology sa bata.”</i></p>
U10	AI application Guidance	Regulating AI application Usage	Skepticism with AI Communication	<p><i>“Yan na yung papasok na yung part ng teacher tsaka yung magulang na lagi sila magkateam up, di pwedeng lagi si teacher lang kasi samin ilang oras lang si ata pagdating sa bahay. Pagdating sa bahay mas malaki yung</i></p>

oras ng magulang na dapat nasusubaybayan nila, so dapat magkakaran ng team-up si teacher atsaka si parent para bigyan ng limited time ng nasa bahay for gadget then tuturuan mo din sya kahit paano sa libro magbasa di puro AI. Kumbaga ituro kay bata na icompare si books tsaka si AI, ano yung magiging impact sa bata ganun din ang gagawin sa school. So, para hindi mawala yung study habit ng bata kailangan sa bahay at sa school may ginagawa sila.”

U9	AI identity	AI's Different Roles	AI's Perceived Identity (Who is AI?)	<i>“Ano lang din, hindi ako fully syempre ano kasi nga yung natanong ko ay gamot edi syempre nakalagay dun sabi ni Meta AI para mas sure ka kailangan mo mag ano sa doctor. Ayun nakalagay naman dun, parang meron silang mga reminder. Parang may ano sila.”</i>
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U9	Professional identity	AI's Different Roles	AI's Perceived Identity (Who is AI?)	<i>“Kukuha lang akong idea, kaya pag ano sasabihin saken ni Doc nung first na bagong bago pa lang akong</i>
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mommy parang mga 4 months 6 months edi nagtanong ako kay Doc sabi ko “Doc bawal po bang uminom ng uminom pa ng water yung baby? Milk pa lang?” Sabi nya saan mo nalaman yun Ginoogle mo yan no sabi nung pedia ng baby ko. Kasi parang ano nga sinearch ko, pwede na bang uminom ng gantong months na baby. ”

U9	AI as a call to friend	AI's Different Roles	AI's Perceived Identity (Who is AI?)	<i>“Ito yung estudyante ko may gamot yung baby ko na natira tapos meron sugat yung estudyante ko, sinearch ko pwede ba yung gamot na yun sa gantong ano, gantong skin ano nya allergy nya. Kasi yung anak ko nagka-allergy tapos sinearch ko kung pwede kasi wala daw syang gamot eh, yun tiningnan ko kung pwede. Maibibigay naman nila yung detail ano eh.”</i>
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U4	AI as friend	AI's Different Roles	AI's Perceived Identity (Who is AI?)	<i>“Oo nagagamit ko sya, halimbawa, yung sa anak ko, minsan nag-away kami ng anak ko. ‘Di naman nag-away, kumbaga di ko lang sya naintindihan. “How to deal with</i>
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*teenagers” ganyan kasi teenager na
yung anak ko.”*

APPENDIX B Figure 1. Proof of Meta AI and Canva Usage by Teachers

The research participants were asked to provide proof of their usage of Meta AI and Canva. Appendix B provides prompt commands for inquiring about various subject topics, recipes, and medications. Some are finished instructional materials created using Canva.

